

**NATIONAL INNOVATION CAPABILITY ENABLERS AND OUTCOMES,
CORRUPTION, AND PROGRESSION TO HIGHER STAGES OF CBDC ADOPTION**

by

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ABSTRACT

Central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) have garnered a lot of interest from scholars, practitioners, and policymakers alike. A survey of the literature that has explored country characteristics as determinants of a country's CBDC adoption suggests a multifaceted landscape shaped by a confluence of political, legal, economic, financial, technological, social, and cultural factors. However, less is known about the role that the national system of innovation (NSI) characteristics may play in the adoption of a CBDC. To fill this research gap, this dissertation explored how five national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human research and capital, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) influenced a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Further, it examined the role that corruption—defined as the abuse of entrusted power (or public office) for private gain—played as a moderator, i.e., whether it strengthened or weakened the impact of the five national innovation enablers and the two national innovation outcomes on a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption, respectively.

Analyzing a unique dataset compiling archival data gathered from the CBDC Tracker, Global Innovation Index, Global Governance Indicators, Corruption Perceptions Index, and Worldwide Corruption Index by employing ordered logistic regression, the study in this dissertation found that none of the five national innovation capability enablers—institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication—had statistically significant positive impact on a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption. However, creative outputs—one of the two national innovation capability outcomes—were found to have statistically significant positive impact on a country's progression to higher

stages of CBDC adoption, while the other national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs) did not. Further, corruption was found to play a moderating role in the case of two national innovation capability enablers. Corruption positively moderated the relationship between institutions and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption, whereas corruption negatively moderated the relationship between market sophistication and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption. In other words, the positive relationship between institutions and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption was stronger in countries with lower levels of corruption than in those with higher levels of corruption, whereas the positive relationship between market sophistication and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption was stronger in countries with higher levels of corruption than in those with lower levels of corruption.

Keywords: Central bank digital currency (CBDC) adoption, national innovation capability, corruption

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Background

The evolution of digital payments has significantly transformed the way we conduct financial transactions. However, the current ecosystem is fraught with challenges, including security vulnerabilities, inefficient processes, and a lack of transparency. As technology advances, there is a pressing need to reimagine the future of payments. Recent research has highlighted critical issues within the existing payment landscape, particularly regarding the importance of robust security measures in the context of Internet of Things (IoT) devices (Bhutta et al., 2023). Neither the integration of blockchain technology which has emerged as a potential solution to address security concerns and enhance the overall efficiency of payment systems nor mobile payments are not without their drawbacks, although they both offer convenience and flexibility. The lack of standardized processes and security protocols can lead to various vulnerabilities as well as infringement upon consumer rights and interests in this domain (Li and Shen, 2023). Further, the traditional credit card payment system has come under scrutiny for its potential to exacerbate consumer debt. Predatory billing practices and high-interest rates contribute to financial hardship for many individuals. As a result, there is a growing interest in exploring alternative payment methods, such as central bank digital currencies (CBDCs), which could offer greater transparency, efficiency, and financial inclusion.

Central bank money refers to the money that is a liability of the central bank. In the United States, there are currently two types of central bank money: physical currency issued by the U.S. Federal Reserve and digital balances held by commercial banks at the Federal Reserve. A central bank digital currency (CBDC) is the digital form of a country's fiat currency, regulated and issued by the Central Bank. In the United States, the Federal Reserve (Central Bank)

controls the supply of money and issues physical United States dollars into circulation of the economy. A CBDC would differ from existing digital money (e.g., bank accounts, payment apps or through online transactions) because it would be a liability of the Federal Reserve, not that of a commercial bank. The U.S. Federal Reserve has made no decision on issuing a CBDC and would only proceed with the issuance of a CBDC with an authorizing law, including Congressional approval.

A CBDC is distinct from a cryptocurrency or a stablecoin. Cryptocurrencies are digital currencies exchanged between people and various entities on a decentralized system and not issued by governments or other financial institutions. Not backed up by a central public authority or within the banking system, they are not considered as legal tender and users are not protected from price volatility, theft because of hacking or when cryptocurrency firms collapse. Stablecoins are designed to be more stable in value by having their value tied to that of another asset. The value of a stablecoin may be pegged to the value of a sovereign currency such as the US dollar or Euro, or other crypto-assets or commodities, or supported by algorithm. There are three types of stablecoins: collateralized, uncollateralized, or algorithm-based.

The CBDC process works similarly across other countries, where the Central Bank issues physical forms of currency, what we consider cash. Technological innovations and the progression towards the complete digitization of money have shifted how countries, individuals, and organizations transact amongst each other. Transacting internationally has especially become a very digitized process, often not involving physical cash at all. The digitization of money movement over recent years, expedited ten-fold during the pandemic, has prompted intense discussion of how the way we transact will evolve in the future. Bitcoin, an entirely digital

currency, has prompted national governments to explore their own options for a completely digital currency. Countries across the globe have started research and deployment of CBDCs.

Since 2008, and the global financial crisis, there has been some indication and concern that people are losing faith in the current financial system that exists. A large movement that has arisen is the decentralization of money, or cryptocurrency (Ogachi et al., 2021). The key feature of this technology is that there is a finite supply, or a fixed amount. For example, Bitcoin, the most notable cryptocurrency, has a capped supply of 21 million. This differs substantially from the centralized issuance of currency by central banks. For example, when central banks want to issue more fiat currency (for example, United States dollar), they simply just print more supply to circulate into the economy. The growth and emergence of Bitcoin has been seen as a direct threat to central banks across the globe (Alonso et al., 2021). Most importantly, it affirms that the perception of our system and fiat currency is changing. This is particularly revolutionary because the “perception” of currency is what allows the system to function (Ogachi et al., 2021).

The complete digitization of money over the last several years has challenged the traditional notion that “cash is king.” Most recently, the global COVID-19 pandemic further progressed the complete digitization of money (Rennie & Steele, 2021). During the pandemic, transactions were made using digital banking tools and people were discouraged from using cash and coins because of the potential transmission of the virus. Europe and the West have moved towards contactless payments through mobile phone applications that allow real-time payments (Ogachi et al., 2021). Certain Nordic countries such as Sweden led the pack in moving to a cashless society. In Sweden, up to half of the banks no longer dealt in cash, and 7/10 of their citizens or 70% expressed optimism that they could do without cash at all. Other European

nations such as the United Kingdom showed dramatic declines with cash transactions which represented only 34% of all transaction in 2017.

The pandemic further exploited the deficiencies that exist with physical currency such as cash. Specifically, when over 131 countries across the globe committed direct cash transfers to assist people through the crisis and provide economic assistance (Rennie & Steele, 2021). During the pandemic, governments deployed emergency payments with existing systems including tax records and social security networks to identify recipients and issue payments. The existing infrastructure of deploying these payments proved to be a slow process and highlighted significant shortcomings with payment systems across the globe.

Challenges of the pandemic, specifically, the issuance of the emergency funds sparked the accelerated interest in digital currencies to combat the problems that exist with the current payment infrastructure (Rennie & Steele, 2021). At the beginning of the pandemic, there was very little discussion about the need for central bank digital currencies (CBDCs). Recent statistics show that 80% of banks have undertaken conceptual work on digital currencies, 40% have progressed with experiments or proofs of concept and another 10% have developed pilot projects

It has been 14 years since the new electronic payment system Bitcoin was born. The growth and emergence of Bitcoin, a decentralized currency, has been seen as a direct threat to central banks across the globe (Alonso et al., 2021). The awakening of a decentralized digital currency has caused countries to rush the development of their own completely digital currency, otherwise known as a CBDC. Central bank digital currencies are expected to reduce currency issuance and circulation costs and broaden the scope of monetary policy (Jun & Yeo, 2021). The arguments for this technology highlight that there will be significant improvements to the

financial system. Countries rushing to develop their own digital currency is also indication that decentralized currency is seen as a direct threat competing with central banks. Indeed, China, Germany, South Korea, Iran, United States, Russia, and India are among the many nations that have piloted or are currently piloting CBDCs. Four nations have already launched CBDCs: In 2017, the Bahamas introduced Sand Dollars, a retail CBDC based on tokens; in 2021, Zimbabwe introduced ZIG; in 2021, Nigeria introduced e-Naira; and in 2023, Jamaica introduced JAM-DEX, a retail CBDC.

Problem Statement

Recently, there has been a considerable increase in the number of studies examining the factors that impact CBDC adoption. One of the major empirical research themes in the CBDC literature is concerned with examining country characteristics as determinants for the adoption of a CBDC. Studies have found a wide range of political, legal, economic, financial, technological, social, and cultural factors. While the existing studies are helpful, they do not fully explore how country-level innovation processes may influence the adoption of a CBDC. However, systems of innovation (SI)—“the elements and relationships which interact in the production, diffusion, and use of new, and economically useful knowledge” (Lundvall, 1992, p. 11)—have been understudied. Little is known about how conditions enabling national innovation capabilities and their outcomes might play a role in adopting a CBDC, at a time when CBDCs are considered as a significant innovation in the financial landscape. Against this backdrop, adopting the national system of innovation (NIS) perspective (Freeman, 1987) seems highly helpful. This perspective argues that innovation capability is an evolutionary learning process (Nelson, 1988) that results from the mutual interactions and complementarities between several, but not necessarily all, institutional conditions (Nelson, 2008; Nelson and Winter, 1982), and the entire evolutionary

learning yields relatively stable and coherent innovation outcomes for countries, though they are not necessarily similar across the countries.

Purpose of the Study

The study in this dissertation explored the extent to which the five national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructures, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and their two outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) may impact a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption, respectively, by applying the national innovation capability (NIC) framework developed by Khedhaouria and Thurik (2017). Further, the study examined the role that corruption—defined as the abuse of entrusted power (or public office) for private gain—may play in moderating the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers/outcomes and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption, especially when corruption is thought to play a dual role depending on various institutional conditions. That is, corruption can serve as a helping hand because it might be an efficient lubricant in rigid economic regulatory and bureaucratic environments (Bjorvatn and Søreide, 2005), while at the same time it can mimic a grabbing hand that increases rent-seeking costs (Bliss and di Tella, 1997; Aidt, 2023). Therefore, corruption may strengthen or weaken the relationship between the five national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructures, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Corruption also may strengthen or weaken the relationship between the two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and a country's progression to higher stages of CBDC adoption. According to the foregoing theory and logic, I proposed and tested four hypotheses as follows.

- Hypothesis 1: Stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will positively impact the possibility that a nation will advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption.
- Hypothesis 2: Stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will positively impact the possibility that a nation will advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption.
- Hypothesis 3: Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.
- Hypothesis 4: Corruption moderates the relationship between the two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

To test these four hypotheses, the study employed a quantitative research design that collected data from five archival sources, namely, the CBDC Tracker, the Global Innovation Index (GII), the Control of Corruption Index within the World Governance Indicators (WGI), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI) to operationalize all the variables included in this study.

Dependent variable. CBDC adoption stage. The dependent variable of the study was a country's CBDC adoption stage, which was operationalized by assigning a value of 1 to research, a value of 2 to development (or proof of concept), a value of 3 to pilot, and a value of 4 to

launched (Auer et al., 2021; Le et al., 2023). As such, the dependent variable was operationalized as a categorical variable.

Independent variables. Seven NSI characteristics. The independent variables of the study were the five national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs). They were operationalized using the seven corresponding pillars within the Global Innovation Index (GII). The GII is a composite index that is comprised of two sub-indexes—innovation input index and innovation output index. The innovation input sub-index measures the elements that enable and facilitate innovation, encompassing five pillars: institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication. The innovation output sub-index measures the outcomes of innovative activities within a country, including two pillars: knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs. For each pillar, country scores range from 0 (lowest) to 100 (highest) in terms of national innovation inputs or outputs. As such, all the independent variables will be operationalized as continuous variables.

Moderating variable. Corruption. The moderator variable of the study was corruption. Three corruption indexes—the control of corruption index within the World Governance Indicators ranging from -2.5 (highest corruption) to 2.5 (lowest corruption), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) ranging from 0 (highest corruption) to 100 (lowest corruption), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI) ranging from 0 (lowest corruption) to 100 (highest corruption). As such, the moderator variable was operationalized as a continuous variable.

Control variables. I controlled for two variables—GDP and interest rate— that have been found to impact a country’s CBDC adoption stage (Maryaningsih et al., 2022; Koparan, 2025) using World Bank data.

Statistical procedures. Because a country’s CBDC adoption stage was operationalized as a categorical dependent variable as described above, I employed logistic regression. This procedure is most suitable for modeling and predicting the probability of a categorical outcome based on independent variables, whether continuous categorical or continuous (Agresti, 2013; Long and Freese, 2006). Although linear regression is a preferred statistical method for modeling and predicting the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables while controlling for the effects of other variables, its application is limited to situations where the dependent variable is continuous, and is not appropriate for categorical variables, which are distinct and have no intrinsic order. CBCD researchers have relied on a variety of statistical methods including binary logistic regression, ordered logistic regression, multinomial logistic regression, depending on how they operationalized the status of CBDC initiatives (Dong et al., 2024; Kacker and Sinha, 2024; Koparan, 2025; Le et al., 2023; Luu et al., 2023; Umar et al., 2024). This study employed ordered logistic regression as a primary statistical method (McCullagh, 1980), while employing binary logistic regression after performing appropriate variable transformation to test the hypotheses for robustness check.

Results. Hypothesis 1 was not supported. None of the five national innovation capability enablers—institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, business sophistication—had positive impact on a country’s advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Hypothesis 2 was supported in the case of creative outputs, but not in the case of knowledge and technology outputs. That is, creative outputs were found to have positive

impact on a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Hypothesis 3 was supported in the case of institutions and market sophistication, but not in the case of human capital and research, infrastructure, and business sophistication. That is, corruption positively moderated the relationship between institutions and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Corruption negatively moderated the relationship between market sophistication and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Hypothesis 4 was not supported in either case of knowledge and technology outputs or creative outputs. That is, corruption moderated neither the relationship between knowledge and technology outputs and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption nor the relationship between creative outputs and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

Significance of Study

It is expected that businesses may benefit from the study in several ways. First, businesses may find it helpful as they seek to understand factors influencing countries' decisions to adopt CBDCs because they can revolutionize the availability of banking services and payment transactions. In particular, by educating themselves on the impact of creative outputs and the interplay between corruption and institutions and the interplay between corruption and market sophistication, current major players in the private sector, such as multinational enterprises, FinTech startups, and financial institutions, can identify potential investments for new market entry. For example, FinTech, financial services, and e-commerce companies can use the study findings to develop market entry strategies to adjust to rapidly changing global payment systems.

Second, businesses can leverage the abovementioned national innovation capability enablers and outcomes to pursue proactive risk management and compliance strategies. Implementing CBDCs creates better payment systems, which decrease costs while improving

operational performance. As such, businesses should analyze their operational potential as consumers or intermediaries for CBDCs and explore cost-saving options by participating in the CBDC ecosystem. For example, businesses can identify and serve new customer segments through financial inclusion enabled by CBDCs, allowing them to create inclusive products for market expansion.

Third, the study findings can help businesses develop profitable financial innovation products that match upcoming CBDC standards. For example, businesses can offer CBDC transaction applications and payment gateways and create security protocols appropriate for a country's innovation conditions.

Theoretical Framework

The underlying theoretical framework for the study was national systems of innovation (NSI). NSI is the most prevalent conceptual framework for understanding innovation processes at the level of the economy. NSI was first described by Lundvall (1985) who used the term to describe the relations and interactions between R & D laboratories and technological institutes on the one hand, and the production system on the other. The national system innovation (NSI) perspective considers innovation capability as an evolutionary learning process (Nelson, 1988; Nelson and Winter, 1982) that occurs within institutional structures. A country's innovation capability emerges when institutional structures are equipped with appropriate institutions that develop human capital through appropriate education and research systems, build common infrastructures to enable knowledge sourcing and transfer, and facilitate market and business conditions to absorb, adopt and implement foreign advanced technologies (Nelson and Winter, 1982, Reddy, 1997).

In this perspective, the key driving force of innovation capability “is assimilation, learning to do effectively what countries at the frontier have been doing, often for some time” (Nelson, 2008: 16). In particular, Kthedhaouria and Thurik (2017) created the national innovation capability (NIC) framework from the NIS perspective to explain how the five conditions of innovation capability (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) interact and support one another to produce the two outcomes of innovation capability (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs). The foundation for the framework is the Global Innovation Index 2015 whose structure is presented below.

In addition, the study applied the concept of corruption which is known to both facilitate and hinder economic development depending on the context. That is, corruption can serve as a helping hand because it might be an efficient lubricant in rigid economic regulatory and

bureaucratic environments (Bjorvatn and Søreide, 2005), while at the same time it can mimic a grabbing hand that increases rent-seeking costs (Bliss and di Tella, 1997; Aidt, 2023).

Research Questions

This study explored the national system of innovation (NIS) characteristics as determinants of CBDC adoption by focusing on the five national innovation capability enablers and the two national innovation capability outcomes (Khedhaouria and Thurik, 2017). Further, it examined the moderating role of corruption in the relationships stated above. A research model of a country’s CBDC adoption used for the study is presented below.

Figure 1 Seven NIS Characteristics and Corruption as Determinants of CBDC Adoption

Hypotheses

The four hypotheses that flow from the model depicted above are presented below.

Hypothesis 1: Stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will

positively impact the possibility that a nation will advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 1 is that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between a country's national innovation capability enablers and its advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

Hypothesis 2: Stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will positively impact the possibility that a nation will advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 2 is that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between a country's national innovation capability outcomes and its advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

Hypothesis 3: Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 3 is that the interaction between corruption and the national innovation capability enablers does not significantly predict the advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

Hypothesis 4: Corruption moderates the relationship between the two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 4 is that the interaction between corruption and the national innovation capability outcomes does not significantly predict the advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

Assumptions

The five main assumptions of the study are as follows. First, the national systems of innovation (NSI) influenced a country's decision to advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Second, the

national innovation capacity (NIC) framework proposed by Kthedhaouria and Thurik (2017) is a conceptual framework that captures the essential elements of the NSI. Third, my archival data sources—namely, CBDC Tracker, GII (Global Innovation Index), World Governance Indicators (WGI), Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and Global Corruption Index (GCI)—are as accurate and credible as practically possible. I recognize that although they are all widely used in academic research, there may be some built-in errors or biases. Fourth, the constructs used in the study, such as CBDC adoption, national innovation capability enablers and outcomes, and corruption, can be quantitatively operationalized using the indicators available in the aforementioned archival sources. Fifth, the study's sample included all the CBDC initiatives from January 2014 to February 2025 available on the CBDC Tracker, so it can be generalizable to a larger population of countries.

Limitations

The three main limitations of the proposed study are described as follows. First, when operationalizing the variables included in the study, I relied exclusively on the archival data and did not gather any primary data via surveys or interviews, which kept me from getting firsthand information. Second, using the CBDC Tracker as a sampling framework, I generated a dataset combining the CBDC Tracker, GII, COCI, CPI, and GCI, resulting in missing variables. Third, the study findings should be evaluated with great caution because correlations between variables cannot establish cause-and-effect relationships.

Delimitations

The five delimitations of the study are described as follows. First, the study focused only on the NIS and corruption and did not consider other country-level characteristics affecting the adoption of a CBDC. Second, the study excluded qualitative approaches to data collection, such as

structured interviews, which could provide more nuanced insights. Third, the study operationalized the adoption of a CBDC in terms of the four CBDC adoption stages (research, proof of concept, pilot, and launched) based on the CBCD Tracker and did not consider other CBDC implementation processes. Fifth, cryptocurrencies or stablecoins were not included in the study because they are distinct from CBDCs.

Definition of Key Terms and Concepts

Below are key terms and concepts related to CBDCs, national innovation capability, and corruption.

CBDC, Cryptocurrencies, and Stablecoins. CBDC stands for Central Bank Digital Currency, which is a digital form of central bank money widely available to the general public. Central bank money refers to the money that is a liability of the central bank. In the United States, there are currently two types of central bank money: physical currency issued by the U.S. Federal Reserve and digital balances held by commercial banks at the Federal Reserve. A CBDC would differ from existing digital money (e.g., bank accounts, payment apps or through online transactions) because it would be a liability of the Federal Reserve, not that of a commercial bank. The U.S. Federal Reserve has made no decision on issuing a CBDC and would only proceed with the issuance of a CBDC with an authorizing law, including Congressional approval.

Cryptocurrencies are digital currencies exchanged between people and various entities on a decentralized system and not issued by governments or other financial institutions. Because cryptocurrencies are not backed up by a central public authority or within the banking system, they are not considered as legal tender and users are not protected from price volatility, theft because of hacking, or when cryptocurrency firms collapse. Stablecoins, which are a form of cryptocurrency, are designed to be more stable in value by having their value tied to that of

another asset. The value of a stablecoin may be pegged to the value of a sovereign currency such as the US dollar, or other crypto-assets or commodities, or supported by algorithm. Stablecoins can fall into two categories: collateralized or uncollateralized/algorithm. For collateralized stablecoins, there are two different kinds: off-chain collateralized stablecoins and on-chain collateralized stablecoins. Off-chain collateralized stablecoins which are backed by traditional assets such as bank deposits or other cash-like assets are referred to as “off-chain” because unlike crypto assets, they are not represented by tokens on a blockchain. On-chain collateralized stablecoins which are backed by crypto assets that can be represented by tokens on a blockchain are referred to as “on-chain.

CBDC Tracker is an open-source project aimed at providing a comprehensive information resource for world CBDC initiatives. Its main components are Dashboard, CBDC Information Card, Timelines and Time Slider, News Aggregator, Watchlist Tool. It categorizes each CBDC initiative since January 2014 using five status classifications: cancelled, research, development (proof of concept), pilot, and launched.

The Global Innovation Index (GII), published by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), is a composite index that measures national innovation capabilities and performance by combining two sub-indexes—innovation input index and innovation output index. The innovation input sub-index measures the elements that enable and facilitate innovation, encompassing five pillars: institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication. The innovation output sub-index measures the results of innovative activities within a country, including two pillars: knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs. Each pillar consists of 3 sub-pillars, each of which is comprised of 2-5 indicators. Country scores range from 0 to 100, where 0 corresponds to the lowest national

innovation capabilities and performance and 100 to the highest national innovation capabilities and performance.

Corruption is defined as the abuse of entrusted power (or public office) for private gain. While corruption can take many shapes and forms, the three most common behaviors include (1) public servants demanding or taking money or favors in exchange for services; (2) politicians misusing public money or granting public jobs or contracts to their sponsors, friends, and families; and (3) individuals, business owners, and corporations bribing officials to get lucrative deals. Corruption incurs not only political and economic costs but also social and environmental costs. I operationalized corruption using three databases, each of which is described below.

The World Governance Indicators (WGI) report on six broad dimensions of governance: voice and accountability, regulatory quality, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, rule of law, government effectiveness, and control of corruption. Control of corruption captures perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as “capture” of the state by elites and private interests. It is an aggregate indicator combining views of a large number of enterprise, citizen and expert survey respondents. Country scores range from -2.5 to +2.5, where -2.5 corresponds to the lowest control of corruption and 2.5 to the highest control of corruption.

The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) is a composite index, published by the non-governmental organization Transparency International since 1995, that scores and ranks countries by their perceived levels of public sector corruption, as assessed by experts and business executives. The CPI generally defines corruption as an abuse of entrusted power for private. Since 2012, the CPI has been ranked on a scale from 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean).

The Global Corruption Index (GCI) covers 196 countries and territories measures the corruption risk exposure deriving from both the public and private sectors. It also includes issues related to white collar crimes and more specifically to money-laundering and terrorism financing. Based on as many as 42 internationally recognized variables, it encompasses two subindexes—corruption and white-collar crimes—for both a global risk overview and a more nuanced risk assessment. Country scores are presented on a 0-100 scale, where 0 corresponds to the lowest risk (corruption) and 100 to the highest risk (corruption).

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

Different Types of Money

Studies have conceptualized a CBDC as a form of money by highlighting its features distinct from those of other types of money. The Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures (CPMI, 2015) was one of the first who put CBDCs in the context of different types of money by examining the physical or digital state of money tokens and whether their exchange can occur in a peer-to-peer manner or requires a financial intermediary. Bjerg (2017) defined a CBDC in relation to the three kinds of money constituting the existing monetary system (i.e., cash, bank money and central bank reserves) through the lack of one of the three features—electronic, universally accessible, and central bank issued. As illustrated below, a CBDC integrates all of the three features, thus potentially competing with each of them.

Figure 2 CBDC vs. Existing Forms of Money

Bech and Garratt (2017) introduced a new taxonomy of money by combining those three features of CBDCs (i.e., electronic, universally accessible, and central-bank issued) discussed above in Bjerg (2017) and the three main characteristics of central bank cryptocurrencies (CBCCs) illustrated below—which are distinct from cash, commodity money, bank deposits—in that CBCCs are not only electronic but also are not the liability of anyone, while at the same time featuring peer-to-peer exchange (CPMI, 2015)

Figure 3 Cryptocurrency vs. Existing Forms of Money

Bech and Garratt (2017)’s taxonomy presented below classified money into 11 categories— (a) cash; (b) commodity; (c) bank deposits/mobile money; (d) virtual currency; (e) settlement or reserve accounts; (f) local currency; (g) cryptocurrency; (h) cryptocurrency (wholesale); (i)

CBCC (retail), and (j)CBCC (wholesale) through the lack of one of the four properties: issuer (central bank or other); form (electronic or physical); accessibility (universal or limited); and transfer mechanism (centralized or decentralized, i.e., peer-to-peer). The Venn-diagram which is called the money flower presented below shows how the two potential types of CBCC (the dark grey shaded area)—retail CBCC accessible to the general public) and wholesale CBCC available only to financial institutions—fit into the overall monetary landscape.

Figure 4 CBCCs within the Money Flower: A Taxonomy of Money

The Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructure (CPMI, 2018) described a CBDC as “a digital form of central bank money that is different from balances in traditional reserve or settlement accounts” by putting it in the context of other types of money (i.e., cash, bank deposits, CB reserves and settlement accounts, private digital tokens for wholesale only) in the form of the money flower (Bech and Garratt, 2017). The Venn-diagram presented below illustrates the four key properties of money: issuer (central bank or not), form (digital or

physical), accessibility (widely or restricted) and technology (account-based or token-based). Money is typically based on one or two basic technologies: tokens of stored value (e.g., cash and many digital currencies) or accounts (e.g., balances in reserve accounts and most forms of commercial bank money). Token-based money (or payment systems) rely on the ability of the payee to verify the validity of the payment object, whereas systems based on account money depend on the ability to verify the identification of the account holder (Kahn and Roberds, 2009).

Figure 5 CBDCs within the Money Flower: A Taxonomy of Money

The three forms of CBDCs (the dark grey shaded area) are situated at the center of the money flow. Two forms are token-based—CB digital tokens (general purpose) which are primarily targeted at retail transactions but also available for broader use and CB digital tokens (wholesale only) which are restricted-access digital settlement tokens for wholesale payment and settlement transactions. The other form is account-based—CB accounts (general purpose) provided to all agents in the jurisdiction.

Adrian and Griffoli (2021) distinguished among five different types of money—(a) central bank money; (b) cryptocurrency; (c) b-money, currently issued by banks; (d) electronic money (e-money), offered by new private sector providers; and (e) investment money (i-money), issued by private investment funds—by highlighting four attributes of means of payment: type, value, backstops, and technology. In other words, these five types of money are differentiated from each other, depending on (1) type—whether they are a claim on underlying assets or an independent object, (2) value—whether can be redeemed into domestic notes and coins at a fixed face value or at a variable rate, (3) backstops—whether they benefit from government backstops, and (4) technology—whether they are settled in a centralized or decentralized fashion. Note that centralized b-money (e.g., debit cards, checks, and wire) and centralized e-money like stored-value facilities (AliPay, WeChat Pay, M-Pesa) are digital forms of money backed by fiat currency but not issued by the monetary authority and are therefore not considered CBDCs.

Figure 6 Five Different Types of Money

Kiff et al. (2020) compared five main types of digital currency—(a) retail CBDC; (b) synthetic CBDC; (c) electronic b-money and centralized e-money; (d) asset-backed stablecoins; (e) payment crypto-assets cash—based on whether the digital currency is (1) issued by a central bank, (2) deemed legal tender, (3) central bank backed, (4) pegged to a fiat currency, (5) allows for peer-to-peer transfers, and (6) can be programmed. As shown below, retail CBDC is the only digital currency that is issued by a central bank, deemed legal tender, central bank backed, pegged to a fiat currency, allows for peer-to-peer transfers, and can be programmed.

Figure 7 Retail Money Key Attributes

Most recently, Dionysopoulos et al. (2024) proposed a money classification where CBDCs are juxtaposed against the six different types of money (i.e., deposits, eMoney, cryptocurrency, P. Metals, cash, and reserves) in terms of the seven features of money, which include medium of exchange, store of value, unit of account, status, convertibility, issuer, access, and availability.

Figure 8 Money Classification

Feature	Deposits	eMoney	Crypto	P. Metals	Cash	Reserves	CBDC
<i>Medium of Exchange</i>	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
<i>Store of Value</i>	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	?
<i>Unit of Account</i>	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
<i>Status</i>	D	D	D	P	P	D	D
<i>Convertibility</i>	✓		✗	✗		✓	?
<i>Issuer</i>	CM	PS	N/A, PS	N/A	CB	CB	CB
<i>Access</i>	A	A	T, A	T	T	A	T, A
<i>Availability</i>	R	W, R, U	W, R, U	W, R, U	W, R, U	W	W, R, U

- Deposits: Funds held in an account at a commercial bank by a customer.
- eMoney: A digital currency stored electronically and issued by a private sector entity.
- Crypto (Cryptocurrency): A digital form of money up ended by a decentralized network utilizing cryptography.
- P. Metals: Naturally occurring metals, such as gold or silver, that have an economic value.
- Cash: Physical currency.
- Reserves: Money held at central banks.
- Status: P (Physical), D (Digital).
- Issuer: CB (Central Bank), CM (Commercial Bank), PS (Private Sector).
- Access: A (Account), T(Token).
- Availability: W(Wholesale), R(Retail), U(Universal).

Definitions of CBDC

While there is no universally accepted definition of what a CBDC is, there are two categories of CBDC definitions: narrow and broad. CBDCs are narrowly defined as “a digital payment instrument, denominated in the national unit of account, that is a direct liability of the CB” (Group of Central Banks, 2020). This narrow definition is also echoed in other similar definitions, such as “an electronic form of CB money that could be used by households and businesses to make payments and store value” (BoE, 2020), “a CB liability offered in digital form for use by citizens and businesses for their retail payments” (ECB, 2020), and “a digital form of CB money that can be used for retail payments”. Such definitions as above mainly focus on their retail and consumer-facing aspects, where some emphasize CBDCs as a strictly wholesale financial instrument that facilitates the execution and settlement of cross-border transactions (BoE, 2020).

CBDCs are distinguished from central bank reserves as “a digital form of central bank (CB) money that is different from balances in traditional reserve or settlement accounts.” CBDCs are not convertible into reserves (Kumhof and Noone, 2021) and differ from other forms of money typically issued by central banks: cash and reserve balances (Griffoli et al., 2018), although Meaning et al.(2018) note that a CBDC already exists in the form of CB reserves when they define it as “any electronic, fiat liability of a CB that can be used to settle payments or as a store of value.” Similarly, Barket al. (2021) described a CBDC as “an electronic, fiat liability of a central bank that can be used to settle payments or as a store of value.” Kumhof and Noone (2021) most comprehensively defined a CBDC to be: “electronic central bank money that (I) can be accessed more broadly than reserves, (II) potentially has much greater functionality for retail transactions than cash, (III) has a separate operational structure to other forms of central

bank money, allowing it to potentially serve a different core purpose, and (IV) can be interest-bearing, and under realistic assumptions would pay a rate that would be different to the rate on reserves.”

In contrast, more broad and abstract definitions of CBDCs describe a CBDC as “a digital representation of a sovereign currency issued by and as a liability of a jurisdiction’s central bank or other monetary authority” (Kiff et al., 2020) or “a digital liability of a CB, or other competent authority, representing a jurisdiction’s sovereign currency available to the private sector” (Dionysopolous et al., 2023). Such broad definitions are advantageous over narrow ones because they can accommodate the full range of CBDC possibilities when different jurisdictions are likely to adopt different CBDC options to accommodate their diverse needs and legal frameworks.

Year	Author(s)	Definition
2018	Meaning et al.	“any electronic, fiat liability of a CB that can be used to settle payments, or as a store of value.”
2018	CPMI	“a digital form of CB money that is different from balances in traditional reserve or settlement accounts.”
2019	Chiu et al.	“a digital form of CB money that can be used for retail payments.”
2020	Group of Central Banks	“a digital payment instrument, denominated in the national unit of account, that is a direct liability of the central bank.”
2020	BoE	“an electronic form of CB money that could be used by households and businesses to make payments and store value.”
2020	ECB	“a CB liability offered in digital form for use by citizens and businesses for their retail payments.”
2020	Kiff et al.	“a digital representation of a sovereign currency issued by and as a liability of a jurisdiction’s central bank or other monetary authority.”

Year	Author(s)	Definition
2021	Barker et al.	“an electronic, fiat liability of a central bank that can be used to settle payments or as a store of value.”
2021	Kumhof and Noone	“electronic central bank money that (I) can be accessed more broadly than reserves, (II) potentially has much greater functionality for retail transactions than cash, (III) has a separate operational structure to other forms of central bank money, allowing it to potentially serve a different core purpose, and (IV) can be interest-bearing, and under realistic assumptions would pay a rate that would be different to the rate on reserves.”
2023	Dionysopolous et al.	“a digital liability of a CB, or other competent authority, representing a jurisdiction’s sovereign currency available to the private sector.”

Retail CBDC Architecture

There are three potential technical architectures for CBDC: 1) direct, intermediate (i.e., hybrid), and indirect (Auer and Böhme, 2020) and two different kinds of CBDC access: (1) token-based access and account-based access.

The CBDC Ecosystem

The CBDC ecosystem consists of three main stakeholder groups: issuers and regulators, intermediaries, and end users. Below is a high-level summary of the CBDC ecosystem described by Koonprasert et al. (2024).

Figure 9 Stakeholders within the CBDC Ecosystem

Issuers and Regulators. At the forefront of the CBDC ecosystem are central banks who are responsible for issuing and regulating a CBDC. To govern the issuance and management of a CBDC, central banks work closely with other government entities and regulators—such as financial market regulators, competition and antitrust authorities, data protection agencies, anti-money laundering (AML) / know your customer (KYC) regulations, and cybersecurity agencies—to develop and implement a comprehensive regulatory and/or monetary legal framework. Their involvement is crucial for ensuring regulatory compliance and promoting the seamless integration of a CBDC into the financial system.

End Users. There are two main groups of end-users: consumers and merchants. Consumers, who include both banked and unbanked individuals, can use a CBDC for daily transactions such as person-to-person (P2P) transfers and making payments to merchants. Merchants, who range from small business owners to large firms, can not only accept a CBDC as a form of payment for goods and services but also manage payroll and settlements with other merchants. In addition, government agencies can be as consumers or merchants, depending on their role as either initiators or beneficiaries in such transactions.

Intermediaries. Intermediaries (e.g., distributors and developers) serve as a conduit between the central bank and the end-users and are essential to the distribution of a CBDC. There are three main types of intermediaries: consumer-facing intermediaries, merchant-facing intermediaries, and developers. Consumer-facing intermediaries provide services to end-user consumers, which include consumer onboarding and account administration, CBDC-related customer support, and integration of a CBDC with financial services. They might include traditional financial institutions (e.g., commercial banks and credit unions), nonbank financial institutions (e.g., big tech and fintech firms), mobile network operators or e-money providers, and government

agencies such as postal operators. Merchant-facing intermediaries (e.g., acquirers and developers) offer services to end-user merchants, which include merchant onboarding, technical support, dispute resolution, and other value-added services. Potential entities include payment system providers (PSPs)—such as merchant acquirers, sub-acquirers, or payment system facilitators—that offer similar services in the existing payments market and independent sales operators (ISOs). Developers, who are also known as infrastructure technology providers, offer technical expertise on a variety of areas, which include development and operations, security, interoperability, offline functionality, and scalability efforts for an efficient CBDC system. Developers are directly hired by central banks to develop and maintain the CBDC infrastructure or hired by intermediaries to build and maintain software applications and services that interact with the CBDC ecosystem.

Core Features of CBDC

The Group of Central Banks (2020) has identified fourteen core features of CBDC, including four instrument features, eight system features, and two institutional features.

Core Feature of CBDC	Description
<i>Instrument Features</i>	
Convertible	To maintain singleness of the currency a CBDC should exchange at par with cash and private money.
Convenient	CBDC payments should be as easy as using cash, tapping with a card or scanning a mobile phone to encourage adoption and accessibility.
Accepted and Available	A CBDC should be usable in many of the same types of transactions as cash, including point of sale and person-to-person. This will include some ability to make offline transactions
Low Cost	CBDC payments should be at very low or no cost to end users, who should also face minimal requirements for technological investment.

Core Feature of CBDC	Description
<i>System Features</i>	
Secure	Both the infrastructure and participants of a CBDC system should be extremely resistant to cyber attacks and other threats. This should also include ensuring effective protection from counterfeiting.
Instant	Instant or near-instant final settlement should be available to end users of the system.
Resilient	A CBDC system should be extremely resilient to operational failure and disruptions, natural disasters, electrical outages and other issues. There should be some ability for end users to make offline payments if network connections are unavailable.
Available	End users of the system should be able to make payments 24/7/365.
Throughput	The system should be able to process a very high number of transactions.
Scalable	To accommodate the potential for large future volumes, a CBDC system should be able to expand.
Interoperable	The system needs to offer sufficient interaction mechanisms with private sector digital payment systems and arrangements to allow easy flow of funds between systems.
Flexible and Adaptable	CBDC system should be flexible and adaptable to changing conditions and policy imperatives.
<i>Institutional Features</i>	
Robust Legal Framework	A central bank should have clear authority underpinning its issuance of a CBDC.
Standards	A CBDC system (infrastructure and participating entities) will need to conform to the appropriate regulatory standards (eg entities offering transfer, storage or custody of CBDC should be held to equivalent regulatory and prudential standards as firms offering similar services for cash or existing digital money).

CBDC Designs and Models

The emergence of CBDCs has ignited a global debate about the future of money. As digital economies expand, CBDCs offer the potential to enhance financial inclusion, improve payment efficiency, and strengthen monetary policy transmission (Carapella & Flemming, 2020).

However, integrating privacy considerations into CBDC design is a complex challenge. While proponents of CBDCs argue for transparency to mitigate financial crime, critics emphasize the importance of protecting user privacy. This literature review examines the interplay between privacy and openness in CBDC design, exploring the trade-offs and potential solutions to this critical issue. A growing body of research focuses on preserving user privacy within the CBDC ecosystem (Carapella & Flemming, 2020). Some studies propose implementing privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), such as zero-knowledge proofs and homomorphic encryption, to protect sensitive user data. Others advocate for off-chain transaction processing to minimize data collection and analysis. While these approaches offer promising solutions, they often raise concerns about the feasibility of effective anti-money laundering (AML) and counter-terrorism financing (CTF) measures.

Achieving a balance between user privacy and regulatory compliance is essential for successfully implementing CBDCs (Carapella & Flemming, 2020). Several studies explore hybrid models that combine elements of both approaches. For instance, researchers propose tiered privacy levels, where sensitive transaction data is protected for a certain period before being made accessible to authorities for regulatory purposes. Developing robust data governance frameworks is crucial to ensure that collected data is used ethically and responsibly.

National Characteristics as Determinants of CBDC Adoption

One of the major empirical research themes in the CBDC literature is concerned with determining the country-level characteristics that influence the adoption of a CBDC. My preliminary survey of this research stream reveals a multifaceted landscape shaped by a confluence of political, legal, economic, financial, technological, social, and cultural factors. Below are the major findings of the key studies (2022-2023) included in my survey.

Maryaningsih et al. (2022) examined the differences in CBDC adoption across emerging and advanced countries using an ordered probit regression model. Through analyzing a cross-country dataset, they found that wholesale CBDC was more advanced in countries with developed financial markets and greater cross-border transactions, whereas retail CBDC was more advanced in countries with lower financial inclusion and a large informal economy. Further, they found that although cross-border transactions were the most crucial factor influencing wholesale CBDC adoption, different factors affected retail CBDC adoption across emerging and advanced countries. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Variables	Emerging Countries		Advanced Countries	
	Coefficient	Standard Error	Coefficient	Standard Error
DOMCR	0.013	0.010	0.019**	0.010
COMBANK	-0.057*	0.030	0.001	0.028
CC	-0.055	0.054	-0.045	0.030
CAOPEN	2.657**	1.042	1.375	5.177
MOBCELL	0.034**	0.015	-0.031	0.036
INOV	0.257*	0.134	0.109	0.114
HHCONS	-0.031	0.025	-0.085	0.054
SHADOW	0.083**	0.032	0.179	0.144
POP	0.311	0.200	0.921**	0.361
REG	-1.856**	0.815	3.176	2.516
/cut1	20.280***	6.297	20.400*	11.510
/cut2	21.030***	6.351	22.190*	11.620
Observations	78		30	
Log likelihood	-24.577		-15.587	
LR chi2	43.38		28.53	
Prob > chi2	0.000		0.002	
Pseudo R2	0.469		0.478	

Variables	Economic wide CBDC Project		Retail CBDC Project		Wholesale CBDC Project	
	Coefficient	Standard error	Coefficient	Standard error	Coefficient	Standard error
DOMCR	0.012*	0.006	0.011**	0.005		
PRVCR					0.025*	0.018
COMBANK	-0.026*	0.015	-0.024*	0.014		
CC			0.009	0.017		
IPAY					-0.069**	0.032
ATM					0.008	0.007
CAOPEN	1.949**	0.781			4.266*	2.375
TRADE			-1.249**	0.572		
ELACCESS	0.012	0.018				
ELQUAL			0.066	0.041		
MOBCELL	0.017*	0.009	0.014	0.009		
FIXBROAD					-0.023	0.067
INOV	0.127**	0.054	0.149***	0.054	-0.079	0.103
HHCONS	-0.031*	0.019	-0.004	0.017	-0.160**	0.067
SHADOW	0.088***	0.027	0.068***	0.024	0.013	0.046
POP	0.438***	0.137	0.137	0.148	1.118***	0.424
REG	-0.852*	0.500	-0.469	0.510	2.362**	1.106
CBIGAR	-1.676	1.044				
CBIIIPD			-0.397*	0.229	0.405	0.440
/cut1	16.720***	4.047	11.050***	3.736	38.680	33.860
/cut2	17.710***	4.100	12.38***	3.796	39.080	33.870
Observations	109		103		102	
Log likelihood	48.131		-45.779		-20.304	
LR chi2	70.190		52.250		37.040	
Prob > chi2	0.000		0.000		0.000	
Pseudo R2	0.422		0.363		0.477	

Alfar et al. (2023) examined the economic, market, demographic and technical factors that influence central banks' decisions in taking advanced actions to issue CBDC for the period of years between 2013 and 2021. They found that underdeveloped economies were more engaged in issuing CBDC and that better regulations, FDI inflow, young populations, and more urban societies increased the probability of CBDC issuance. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Variables	Pooled OLS	Pooled OLS with lags	Probit model	Probit model with lags	Logit model	Logit model with lags
Log (GDP capita)	-0.0186 (0.0121)		-.0458085*** (.0142936)		-.0433941*** (.0144853)	
Government effectiveness	0.00262 (0.0127)		.0519244*** (.0180807)		.0498222*** (.0186136)	
Rural population	-0.00162*** (0.000406)	-0.00225*** (0.000529)	-.0024744*** (.0008059)	-.001806** (0.00083)	-.0024355*** (.00079)	-0.002*** (0.001)
Access to electricity	0.000128 (0.000355)		-.0006549 (.0005186)		-.000656 (.0005198)	
Internet use	-0.000502 (0.000486)		-.0006216 (.0005486)		-.0006447 (.0005698)	
Young population	0.00275** (0.00135)	0.00395** (0.00177)	.0071955** (.0028306)	.0057** (0.0026)	.0069413** (.003012)	0.0074** (0.003)
Technology exports	0*** (0)		4.28e-13*** (1.05e-13)		4.10e-13*** (1.02e-13)	
Trade in service sector	-0.000411 (0.000319)		-.0015645** (.0006767)		-.0015502** (.0006755)	
Gross capital formation	-0.00235*** (0.000653)		-.008078*** (.0018516)		-.0077713*** (.001853)	
FDI inflow	0.000474 (0.000798)		.0017259** (.0007638)		.0016827** (.0008238)	
M2	-0.000227* (0.000135)		-.0006404** (.0002867)		-.0006078** (.0002971)	
Log(GDP capita) _{t-1}		-0.0281* (0.0158)		-0.04** (0.018)		-0.046*** (0.017)
Government effectiveness _{t-1}		0.00811 (0.0166)		0.047** (0.023)		0.053** (0.023)
Access to electricity _{t-1}		0.000132 (0.000465)		0.001 (0.001)		0.000 (0.001)
Internet use _{t-1}		-0.000803 (0.000636)		-0.001 (0.001)		-0.001 (0.001)
Technology exports _{t-1}		0*** (0)		0*** (0)		0.000*** (0.000)
Trade in service sector _{t-1}		-0.000485 (0.000418)		-0.001** (0.001)		-0.001** (0.001)
Gross capital formation _{t-1}		-0.00342*** (0.000855)		-0.008*** (0.002)		-0.009*** (0.002)
FDI inflow _{t-1}		3.60e-05 (0.00104)		-0.001 (0.001)		-0.001 (0.001)
M2 _{t-1}		-0.000113 (0.000176)		0 (0)		-0.000 (0.000)

Le et al. (2023) examined the factors affecting the different stages of CBDC adoption by 55 countries engaged in CBDC projects from 2014 to 2021 through employing a multinomial

logistic regression method. The study found that anti-money laundering and terrorist financing and the financial market development, inflation and technological factors were the critical determinants of CBDC adoption at different stages. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

	Whole sample		Retail CBDC	Wholesale CBDC
Research	Base outcome			
Proof of Concept				
<i>AML</i>	0.398(0.342)	0.417(0.398)	0.021(0.652)	-0.039(0.698)
<i>FD</i>	2.521*(1.411)	3.281*(1.816)	2.976(3.013)	7.32*(4.083)
<i>INF</i>	-0.024(0.065)	-0.03(0.064)	-0.046(0.108)	0.048(0.306)
<i>GDPPC</i>	-0.006(0.005)	0.009(0.006)	-0.003(0.012)	-0.0001*** (0.0001)
Const	-5.456(2.24)	-6.39*** (2.48)	-4.254(3.877)	0.39(4.702)
Pilot				
<i>AML</i>	-0.313(0.392)	0.725(0.546)	-0.633(1.088)	0.564(0.765)
<i>FD</i>	-0.971(1.862)	-1.162(1.937)	0.579(7.323)	-4.624(4.52)
<i>INF</i>	-0.131(0.128)	-0.029(0.132)	0.419(0.278)	-0.448(0.281)
<i>GDPPC</i>	-0.014*(0.007)	-0.014*(0.008)	-0.45*(0.027)	-0.0001*(0.000)
Const	1.701(2.481)	-2.937(2.947)	0.524(6.46)	3.556(3.942)
Launched				
<i>AML</i>	1.484*(0.867)	3.464*(1.94)	3.179*(1.828)	
<i>FD</i>	-7.614**(3.457)	-11.639*(5.95)	-10.489*(5.713)	
<i>INF</i>	-0.458(0.323)	-0.178(0.307)	-0.246(0.39)	
<i>GDPPC</i>	0.022(0.014)	-0.0001(0.016)	0.004(0.023)	
Const	-9.526(5.901)	-16.57*(9.95)	-15.494(9.75)	
Cancelled				
<i>AML</i>	0.07(0.45)	-0.357(0.593)	0.158(0.614)	
<i>FD</i>	-3.77**(1.79)	-2.875(2.174)	-2.523(2.33)	
<i>INF</i>	-0.279*** (0.183)	-0.65*** (0.23)	0.822*** (0.312)	
<i>GDPPC</i>	0.0004(0.008)	0.005(0.01)	0.008(0.012)	
Const	0.422(2.828)	1.175(3.478)	-1.05(3.45)	
FE control ¹	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. Obs	118	118	84 ²	38 ²
χ^2	41.99***	65.69***	54.56***	24.44**
Pseudo R ²	0.158	0.247	0.331	0.317

Luu et al. (2023) examined the impact of national culture on the decision of countries to adopt a CBDC using Hofstede’s cultural framework (i.e. power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and long-term orientation) to measure different cultural values. The study

found that countries with more power distance, masculinity and long-term orientation cultures were more eager to adopt a CBDC, whereas countries with a cultural value leaning towards uncertainty avoidance are less involved in the adoption of a CBDC. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Statistical Procedure	Ordered Logit Regression				Logistic Regression		
Dependent Variable: CBDC Adoption (2014-2021)	0: Countries are not involved in CBDC stage 1: Countries are in CBDC research progress 2: Countries announced the proof of concept 3: Countries in the pilot adoption stage 4: Countries launched their CBDCs				0=Countries have never declared any formal actions towards CBDC adoption 1=Countries have declared actions formal towards CBDC adoption (research, proof of concept, pilot, or launched)		
Independent Variable: National Culture	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4 (Indulgence Added)	Any CBDC Stage vs. Not Adopted	Retail CBDC Adoption	Wholesale CBDC Adoption
Power Distance	0.006* (p=0.003)	0.007* (p=0.003)	0.008*** (p=0.003)	0.007*** (p=0.002)	0.001** (p=0.000)	0.000 (p=0.001)	0.001** (p=0.001)
Individualism	-0.000 (p=0.004)	0.001 (p=0.004)	0.003 (p=0.003)	-0.003 (p=0.002)	0.001 (p=0.002)	-0.001 (p=0.001)	0.001 (p=0.001)
Masculinity	0.004* (p=0.004)	0.004* (p=0.002)	0.004* (p=0.002)	0.003* (p=0.002)	0.002* (p=0.001)	0.003*** (p=0.001)	-0.001 (p=0.001)
Uncertainty Avoidance	-0.011** (p=0.004)	-0.012** (p=0.004)	- 0.012*** (p=0.003)	- 0.012*** (p=0.003)	- 0.005*** (p=0.002)	- 0.005*** (p=0.002)	-0.002* (p=0.001)
Long-term Orientation	0.006**** (p=0.002)	0.007*** (p=0.002)	0.007*** (p=0.002)	0.004*** (p=0.001)	0.003*** (p=0.001)	0.003*** (p=0.001)	0.001 (p=0.001)
Indulgence	N/A			0.005*** (p=0.001)	N/A		
Year Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Subregional Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Regional Fixed Effects	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Observations	413	413	413	413	413	187	352
R-Squared	0.235	0.286	0.273	0.298	0.303	0.356	0.356

Mohammed et al. (2023) explored the technological, environmental, legal, and economic factors that affect central bank digital currency adoption across 67 countries. The study found that there was a positive relationship between a country’s level of democracy and public confidence in governance and CBDC adoption, while a country’s regulatory quality and income inequality negatively influenced CBDC adoption. A country’s level of network readiness, foreign exchange reserves, and sustainable development goal rank had no relationship with CBDC adoption. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

			Result
H1	Network readiness → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = 0.03, p = 0.41$)	Reject
H2	Sustainable development goals → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.10, p = 0.21$)	Reject
H3	Corruption perception → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = 0.20, p = 0.04$)	Pass
H4	Corruption control → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = 0.04, p = 0.38$)	Reject
H5	Democracy level → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = 0.33, p < 0.01$)	Pass
H6	Regulatory quality → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.37, p < 0.01$)	Pass
H7	Economic freedom → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.15, p < 0.10$)	Reject
H8	Gini coefficient → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.20, p = 0.04$)	Pass
H9	Human development → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.04, p = 0.37$)	Reject
H10	Foreign currency reserve → Adoption status of CBDCs	($\beta = -0.13, p = 0.14$)	Reject

Hsu et al. (2023) provided insights into user perspectives to generate tangible contributions to a user-centric approach of retail CBDC adoption. Their empirical analysis of user sentiments towards commonly identified factors of retail CBDC adoption utilizing a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) validated the importance of user centricity in CBDC design, such as through user needs (e.g., efficiency, integrity, safety, and privacy). The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

				Hypothesized Relationship	Coefficient	Supported?
H1 (+)				H1: Positive	.869	Yes
H2 (+)				H2: Positive	-.013	No
H3 (+)				H3: Positive	-.001	No
H4 (+)				H4: Positive	.895	Yes
H5 (+)				H5: Positive	.216	Yes
H6 (+)				H6: Positive	.250	Yes
H7 (+)				H7: Positive	.248	Yes
H8 (+)				H8: Positive	.251	Yes
H9 (+)				H9: Positive	.251	Yes
H10 (+)				H10: Positive	.135	Yes
H11 (+)				H11: Positive	.500	Yes
H12 (+)				H12: Positive	.495	Yes
H13 (+)				H13: Positive	.006	No

Mohammed et al. (2024) investigated the influence of a country’s financial access and stability—measured in terms of individual financial access, the ownership of credit cards, financing accessibility by firms, offshore loans, financial sanctions, and the ownership structure of financial institutions—on the adoption of retail CBDCs across 71 countries. The study found that countries facing financial sanctions and those with substantial offshore bank loans were more inclined to adopt CBDCs and countries with restricted financial access had a heightened interest in CBDC adoption. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

		Coeff. $p > z$	Result
H1	Financial sanction (SANC) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = 3.47, p = 0.05$)	Pass
H2	Access to banks (ACC) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = 0.32, p = 0.01$)	Pass
H3	Availability of credit financing to firms (FIRMCR) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = -0.12, p = 0.003$)	Pass
H4	Offshore bank loans (DEBT) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = 0.11, p = 0.03$)	Pass
H5	Foreign-owned banks (OWN) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = -0.0001, p = 0.99$)	Reject
H6	Ownership of credit card (FINA) → Adoption of retail CBDCs	($\beta = 0.08, p = 0.007$)	Pass

• Dong et al. (2024) explored the macroeconomic development factors that determine countries' decisions to implement CBDCs in 85 countries spanning the years from 2013 to 2021. They found that higher levels of financial inclusion, net foreign assets, remittances, and income were associated with a higher probability of CBDC adoption, whereas higher values for the Human Development Index, manufacturing value added, and population growth rate were inversely related with the probability of CBDC adoption. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

	Logistics regression			Probit regression		
	1 CBDC1	2 CBDC2	3 CBDC3	1 CBDC1	2 CBDC2	3 CBDC3
LN_DEMOI	18.14** (0.006)	-0.906** (0.036)	-0.299 (0.496)	10.04*** (0.006)	-0.49* (0.052)	-0.163 (0.527)
LN_HDI	-57.46*** (0.001)	-10.36*** (0.000)	-12.56*** (0.000)	-32.19*** (0.001)	-5.798*** (0.000)	-6.875*** (0.000)
LN_ATM	9.588** (0.014)	0.950*** (0.000)	0.947*** (0.000)	5.373** (0.016)	0.512*** (0.001)	0.478*** (0.000)
LN_BM	-16.86*** (0.006)	0.505* (0.094)	0.976*** (0.001)	-9.421** (0.007)	0.318* (0.071)	0.569*** (0.001)
LN_MVA	-18.02*** (0.004)	-1.204*** (0.000)	-1.239*** (0.000)	-10.04*** (0.005)	-0.716*** (0.000)	-0.706*** (0.000)
LN_NFA	1.022*** (0.01)	0.180*** (0.001)	0.243*** (0.000)	0.577** (0.01)	0.108*** (0.001)	0.148*** (0.000)
LN_PRP	0.0801 (0.883)	0.444*** (0.000)	0.808*** (0.000)	0.0269 (0.928)	0.270*** (0.000)	0.455*** (0.000)
LN_POP	-2.286*** (0.001)	-0.634*** (0.001)	-1.380*** (0.000)	-1.301*** (0.001)	-0.358*** (0.000)	-0.789*** (0.000)
COVID	4.053** (0.014)	-0.338 (0.503)	-0.736 (0.124)	2.258** (0.014)	-0.179 (0.515)	-0.429 (0.117)
INCOME_LEV	7.084*** (0.006)	1.491*** (0.001)	0.202 (0.597)	3.955*** (0.006)	0.878*** (0.001)	0.148 (0.5)
CONS.	-29.46 (0.111)	-22.21*** (0.000)	-31.36*** (0.000)	-16.26 (0.112)	-13.17*** (0.000)	-17.84*** (0.000)
N	415	415	415	415	415	415

This table presents the logistic regression, probit regression and ordinary least square results. CBDC stands for CBDC launch status as ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. LN stands for natural log and the abbreviations explanations is given in Table 1.

Kacker and Sinha (2024) examined the role of institutional quality in the development of digital currencies using the World Bank’s World Governance Indicator (WGI) framework for a sample of 92 economies. The WGI framework consists of six governance indicators which include 1) voice and accountability, 2) political stability and absence of violence and terrorism, 3) governance effectiveness, 4) regulatory quality, 5) rule of law, and 6) control of corruption. Utilizing a multinomial logistic regression, the study found that governance factors significantly influenced the level of CBDC development. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: CBDC Development Stage (Odds Ratio)			
	Research	Development	Pilot	Launched
Governance Variable: Voice and Accountability	-0.0030206762	0.0018915385	-0.001501855	0.00087192
Political Stability/Absence of Terrorism	0.0026331881	-0.0010742606	-0.000539668	-0.0089851

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: CBDC Development Stage (Odds Ratio)			
	Government Effectiveness	0.000824119	0.002473473	-0.000796558
Regulatory Quality	0.001269718	0.002358413	-0.001017878	-0.00258242
Rule of Law	0.002682762	-0.002355967	-0.002750527	-0.00199889
Control of Corruption	-0.002437483	0.002506746	0.000126666	-0.00064840

Umar et al. (2024) investigated whether institutional quality influences the adoption of Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDC). To address this question, data from 85 countries spanning from 2013 to 2021 was analysed employing logistic, probit, and ordinary least squares regressions to assess the impact of the independent variables. The results indicated that institutional quality significantly affected CBDC adoption, with higher institutional quality associated with a greater likelihood of adoption. An in-depth analysis revealed that voice and accountability was the most critical factor within the institutional indices that significantly explained CBDC adoption. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Table 3
The impact of institutional quality on CBDC adoption by using logistics regression.

	LNCH (Launch)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
IQ_HUN	1.271*** (0.000)						
IQ_VAT		-0.226 (0.53)					
COC			0.00216 (0.836)				
GE				-0.00778 (0.53)			
RQ					-0.0335*** (0.009)		
ROL						-0.00734 (0.498)	
VA							0.0438*** (0.000)
RP	0.0535*** (0.000)	0.0494*** (0.000)	0.0514*** (0.000)	0.0494*** (0.000)	0.0446*** (0.000)	0.0499*** (0.000)	0.0535*** (0.000)
POP1564	15.35*** (0.005)	13.21*** (0.006)	12.78*** (0.008)	13.21*** (0.006)	13.85*** (0.005)	12.53*** (0.009)	15.35*** (0.005)
ICTGE	0.02 (0.471)	-0.00653 (0.824)	-0.00839 (0.77)	-0.00653 (0.824)	0.00224 (0.942)	-0.00837 (0.773)	0.02 (0.471)
TS	0.0445*** (0.000)	0.0518*** (0.000)	0.0500*** (0.000)	0.0518*** (0.000)	0.0593*** (0.000)	0.0532*** (0.000)	0.0445*** (0.000)
BM	-0.0357*** (0.003)	-0.0272*** (0.006)	-0.0270*** (0.006)	-0.0272*** (0.006)	-0.0279*** (0.007)	-0.0266*** (0.007)	-0.0357*** (0.003)
CBB	0.0501** (0.051)	0.0558** (0.012)	0.0558** (0.013)	0.0558** (0.012)	0.0640*** (0.003)	0.0559*** (0.011)	0.0501** (0.051)
INFL	0.00136 (0.861)	-0.00124 (0.889)	-0.000687 (0.937)	-0.00124 (0.889)	-0.00306 (0.767)	-0.00128 (0.886)	0.00136 (0.861)
ATM	-0.0226* (0.067)	-0.0189* (0.077)	-0.0196* (0.07)	-0.0189* (0.077)	-0.0178* (0.081)	-0.0195* (0.068)	-0.0226* (0.067)
FBB	0.00533 (0.821)	0.0469* (0.054)	0.0397* (0.086)	0.0469* (0.054)	0.0598** (0.013)	0.0474* (0.052)	0.00533 (0.821)
CONS	-14.20*** (0.000)	-13.72*** (0.000)	-13.51*** (0.000)	-13.33*** (0.000)	-12.72*** (0.000)	-13.00*** (0.000)	-16.37*** (0.000)
N	596	596	596	596	596	596	596

Notes: Table 3 represents the relationship between institutional quality and CBDC adoption. These results have been calculated by using logistics regression technique. Parentheses denote *p* values, and ***, **, * represent levels of statistical significance at 1 %, 5 % and 10 % levels, respectively.

Yekta et al. (2024) study examined the factors affecting the issuance of Central Bank cryptocurrency (CBDC) using a mixed-methods approach (qualitative-quantitative). The qualitative section employed the grounded theory method through semi-structured in-depth interviews with 15 experts in the fields of payment systems and financial technologies, selected through purposeful and snowball sampling. In the qualitative phase, after three stages of coding, the affecting components were identified, comprising six main categories (axial, causal conditions, intervening conditions, contextual conditions, strategies, and outcomes), along with 37 subcategories and 190 concepts. In the quantitative section, to validate the categories derived from the qualitative phase, a fuzzy Delphi approach was utilized with input from a panel of experts. Additionally, to test hypotheses based on the validation of relationships among the

categories, a Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach was employed. The statistical population for the quantitative research consisted of all experts, deputies, and managers at the central bank, from which 110 individuals in the payment systems department were selected as the research sample. The results of the quantitative phase confirmed the validity of the identified components. Their research identified multiple factors affecting the issuance of token-based central bank digital currency as well as affirming that the issuance of digital currency paved the way for its social acceptance, emphasizing the necessity for precise policymaking. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Result	t-coefficient	Path coefficient	Route	
			To variable	From variable
Meaningful	2.817	0.381	Central	Causal Conditions
Meaningful	1.998	0.681	Strategies	Contextual Conditions
Meaningful	3.651	0.309	Strategies	Intervening Conditions
Meaningful	2.314	0.124	Strategies	Central
Meaningful	6.248	0.973	Consequences	Strategies

Koparan (2025) showed that higher GDP levels significantly increased the likelihood of active CBDC adoption by 332.1 percent and pilot adoption by 212.6 percent, reflecting the role of economic development. Greater internet usage improved the odds of active adoption by 12.7 percent and pilot adoption by 13.4 percent, while financial inclusion indicators, such as account ownership, increased the likelihood of adoption by 59 percent for active initiatives and 141 percent for pilot projects. Monetary freedom positively influenced active adoption by 31.1 percent, and higher interest rates increase the odds by 20.8 percent. Conversely, business freedom negatively affected active adoption by 27.5 percent and pilot adoption by 29.1 percent, suggesting that countries with strong private-sector digital payment solutions relied less on CBDCs. The key statistical analysis results of their study are presented below.

Predictor	Active				Pilot			
	Odds ratio	Std. err.	z	p> z	Odds ratio	Std. err.	z	p> z
Property rights	1.115*	0.069	1.760	0.079	1.089*	0.053	1.740	0.082
Judicial effectiveness	1.000	0.037	0.010	0.991	1.005	0.033	0.140	0.891
Government integrity	1.034	0.055	0.640	0.524	1.015	0.046	0.330	0.739
Tax burden	0.995	0.041	-0.130	0.900	0.978	0.035	-0.620	0.533
Government spending	1.006	0.024	0.230	0.817	1.000	0.022	-0.010	0.995
Fiscal health	1.021	0.018	1.180	0.237	1.024	0.016	1.500	0.133
Business freedom	0.725***	0.087	-2.690	0.007	0.709***	0.076	-3.220	0.001
Labor freedom	0.980	0.054	-0.370	0.714	1.028	0.051	0.560	0.576
Monetary freedom	1.311**	0.147	2.420	0.016	1.133	0.119	1.190	0.235
Trade freedom	1.002	0.090	0.020	0.980	1.048	0.082	0.610	0.545
Investment freedom	0.982	0.043	-0.420	0.672	0.972	0.037	-0.740	0.461
Financial freedom	0.913*	0.044	-1.880	0.061	0.967	0.039	-0.830	0.407
Financial institution account	1.59***	1.440	2.610	0.009	2.41***	1.780	2.290	0.022
Owns a debit card	0.004	0.021	-1.080	0.279	0.003	0.015	-1.190	0.234
Owns a debit or credit card	0.001	0.000	-1.470	0.140	0.001	0.001	-1.040	0.297
Used phone/int. to check acc. bal.	1.427	1.136	0.620	0.533	5.744	0.404	0.250	0.804
Used phone/int. payments	1.894	1.533	0.360	0.716	15.511	1.105	0.390	0.700
Store money in a fin. inst.	3.587	16.642	0.280	0.783	8.507	0.367	0.500	0.620
Internet usage	1.127**	0.060	2.260	0.024	1.134***	0.053	2.720	0.007
GDP	4.321**	2.926	2.160	0.031	3.126**	1.818	1.960	0.050
Inflation	0.982	0.027	-0.650	0.515	0.972	0.027	-1.030	0.304
Interest rate	1.208**	0.096	2.400	0.017	1.117	0.080	1.540	0.123
GINI index	1.019	0.062	0.310	0.760	1.033	0.054	0.630	0.526
Cons	0.000	0.000	-2.570	0.010	0.000	0.000	-1.640	0.100
R ²	0.53				0.47			

	CBDC: Active	CBDC: Pilot
	A country is conducting research, has a pilot program, or launched a CBDC	A country has initiated a CBDC pilot program
	Odds Ratio	Odds Ratio
Economic Indicators		
GDP	4.321** (p=0.031)	3.126** (p=0.050)
Inflation	0.982 (p=0.515)	0.972 (p= 0.304)
Interest rate	1.208** (p=0.017)	1.117 (p= 0.123)
GINI index	1.019 (p=0.760)	(p=0.526)
Legal and Institutional Environment		
Property rights	1.115* (p=0.079)	1.089* (p=0.082)
Judicial effectiveness	1.000 (p=0.991)	1.005 (p=0.891)
Government integrity	1.034 (p=0.524)	1.015 (p=0.739)
Fiscal Policy and Governance		
Tax burden	0.995 (p=0.900)	0.978 (p=0.533)
Government spending	1.006 (p=0.817)	1.000 (p=0.995)
Fiscal health	1.021 (p=0.237)	1.024 (p=0.133)
Business freedom	0.725*** (0.007)	0.709*** (p=0.001)
Labor freedom	0.980 (p=0.714)	1.028 (p=0.576)
Monetary freedom	1.311** (0.016)	1.133 (p=0.235)
Trade freedom	1.002 (p=0.980)	1.048 (p=0.545)
Investment freedom	0.982 (p=0.672)	0.972 (p=0.461)
Financial freedom	0.913*(p=0.061)	0.967 (p=0.407)
Financial Infrastructure and Access to Financial Services		
Internet usage	1.127** (0.024)	1.134*** (0.007)
Financial institution account	1.59*** (0.009)	2.41*** (0.002)
Owens a debit card	0.004 (p=0.279)	0.003 (p=0.234)
Owens a debit or credit card	0.001 (p=0.140)	0.001 (p=0.297)
Used a mobile phone or the internet to check account balance	1.427 (p=0.533)	0.533 (p=0.804)
Use a mobile phone or the internet to make payments, buy things, or to send or receive money using a financial institution account	1.894 (p=0.716)	15.511 (p=0.700)
Store money using a financial institution	3.587 (p=0.783)	8.507 (p=0.620)
R ²	0.53	0.47

While the existing studies are helpful, they not fully explored how country-level innovation processes may influence the adoption of a CBDC. Against this backdrop, the concept of systems of innovation (SI), which refer to “the elements and relationships which interact in the production, diffusion, and use of new, and economically useful knowledge” (Lundvall, 1992, p. 11) will be introduced in the paragraphs that follow.

National System of Innovation (NSI)

The most prevalent conceptual framework for understanding innovation processes at the level of the economy is the concept of Systems of Innovation (SI). The concept of National System of Innovation (NSI), which traces back to the late 1980s and early 1990s, was developed through the collaboration among Chris Freeman, Richard Nelson and Bent-Åke Lundvall in the International Federation of Institutes for Advanced Study (IFIAS) project. It was Lundvall (1985) who first used the term “national system of innovation” to describe the relations and interactions between R & D laboratories and technological institutes on the one hand, and the production system on the other. Drawing on the notion of ‘The National System of Political Economy’, which was originally articulated by Friedrich List (1789–1864), Freeman (1987) provided a historical account of the rise of Japan as an economic superpower to formally introduce the concept, positing that innovation activities are not just the work of enterprises or individuals. Around the same time, Lundvall (1988) highlighted the importance of adopting a systemic view through studying social interactions between suppliers and customers and their role in stimulating innovation. Later, Freeman (1988), Nelson (1988), and Lundvall (1988) jointly contributed to making the concept as a scholarly concept.

The SI concept was subsequently further developed both conceptually and empirically by many scholars, most notably by Lundvall (1992), Nelson (1993) and the OECD. Whilst not

being a theory per se, the SI is a theory-rich conceptual framework that has recently gained a lot of attention in the field innovation studies (Edquist, 2005). Despite its popularization, the SI concept is still considered as an emerging analytical framework whose definition varies considerably, depending on the characteristics of the system being considered. However, the most cited definition appears to be that of Lundvall (1992), who broadly defined the SI concept as “[t]he elements and relationships which interact in the production, diffusion and use of new, and economically useful knowledge” (pg. 11). Alternative definitions of the concept are provided by other SI scholars (including Edquist, 2005; Freeman, 1987; Metcalfe, 1995). The most important message in SI concept is that actors do not, and cannot, innovate in isolation and hence innovation is a collective and interactive process. Additionally, the SI approach has changed the analytical perspective on innovation from the traditional linear models (e.g. that of a ‘technology push’ and ‘market pull’ or of ‘basic research– applied research– development– diffusion’) to a systemic view of interaction among different actors (Edquist, 2005). Adopting an SI perspective has the potential to facilitate a transition of the rationale for policy intervention from the typically limited input–output (linear) approach to a more ‘systemic efficacy’ approach.

The national system innovation (NSI) perspective considers innovation capability as an evolutionary learning process (Nelson, 1988; Nelson and Winter, 1982) that occurs within institutional structures “in the public and private sectors whose activities and interactions initiate, A country’s innovation capability emerges when institutional structures are equipped with appropriate institutions that develop human capital through appropriate education and research systems, build common infrastructures to enable knowledge sourcing and transfer, and facilitate market and business conditions to absorb, adopt and implement foreign advanced technologies (Nelson and Winter, 1982, Reddy, 1997). In this perspective, the key driving force of innovation

capability “is assimilation, learning to do effectively what countries at the frontier have been doing, often for some time” (Nelson, 2008: 16). Below are several definitions of a national system of innovation:

- "... the network of institutions in the public and private sectors whose activities and interactions initiate, import, modify and diffuse new technologies (Freeman, 1995).
- "... the elements and relationships which interact in the production, diffusion and use of new, and economically useful, knowledge ... and are either located within or rooted inside the borders of a nation state” (Lundvall, 2010)
- "... a set of institutions whose interactions determine the innovative performance ... of national firms." (Nelson, 1993)
- "... the national institutions, their incentive structures and their competencies, that determine the rate and direction of technological learning (or the volume and composition of change generating activities) in a country." (Patel, 1994)
- "... that set of distinct institutions which jointly and individually contribute to the development and diffusion of new technologies and which provides the framework within which governments form and implement policies to influence the innovation process. As such it is a system of interconnected institutions to create, store and transfer the knowledge, skills and artefacts which define new technologies." (Metcalf, 1995)

National Innovation Capability (NIC) Framework

Kthedhaouria and Thurik (2017) created the national innovation capability (NIC) framework from the NIS perspective to explain how the five conditions of innovation capability (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business

sophistication) interact and support one another to produce the two outcomes of innovation capability (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs).

The foundation for the framework is the Global Innovation Index 2015 whose structure is presented below.

Figure 10 The Basic Structure of The Global Innovation Index

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2015)
Innovation Input Subindexes
1st Pillar: Institutions
A. Political Environment 1.1 Political stability 1.2 Government effectiveness B. Regulatory Environment 1.3 Regulatory quality 1.4 Rule of law 1.5 Cost of redundancy dismissal, salary weeks C. Business Environment 1.6 Ease of starting a business 1.7 Ease of resolving insolvency 1.8 Ease of paying taxes
2nd Pillar: Human Capital and Research

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2015)

A. Education

- 2.9 Current expenditure on education, % GNI
- 2.10 Public expenditure on education/pupil, % GDP/cap
- 2.11 School life expectancy, years
- 2.12 PISA scales in reading, maths, & science
- 2.13 Pupil-teacher ratio secondary

B. Tertiary Education

- 2.14 Tertiary enrolment, % gross
- 2.15 Graduates in science & engineering, %
- 2.16 Tertiary inbound mobility, %

C. Research and Development (R&D)

- 2.17 Researchers, FTE/mn pop
- 2.18 Gross expenditure on R&D, % GDP
- 2.19 Quality of scientific research institutions

3rd Pillar: Infrastructure

A. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)

- 3.20 ICT access
- 3.21 ICT use
- 3.22 Government's online service
- 3.23 E-participation

B. General Infrastructure

- 3.24 Electricity output, kWh/cap
- 3.25 Quality of trade & transport infrastructure
- 3.26 Gross capital formation, %GDP

C. Ecological Sustainability

- 3.27 GDP/unit of energy use, 2 000PPP\$/kg oil eq.
- 3.28 Environmental performance
- 3.29 ISO14001certificates/bn PPP\$ GDP

4th Pillar: Market Conditions

A. Credit

- 4.30 Ease of getting credit
- 4.31 Domestic credit to private sector, % GDP
- 4.32 Micro finance gross loans, % GDP

B. Investment

- 4.33 Ease of protecting investors
- 4.34 Market capitalization, % GDP

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2015)
4.35 Total value of stocks traded, % GDP 4.36 Venture capital deals/tr PPP\$ GDP C. Trade and Competition 4.37 Applied tariff rate, weighted mean, % 4.38 Intensity of local competition
5th Pillar: Business Conditions
A. Knowledge Workers 5.39 Knowledge-intensive employment, % 5.40 Firms offering formal training, % firms 5.41 R&D performed by business, % 5.42 R&D financed by business B. Innovation Linkages 5.43 University/industry research collaboration 5.44 State of cluster development 5.45 R&D financed by abroad 5.46 JV-strategic alliance deals/tr PPP\$ GDP 5.47 Patent families filed in 3+offices/bn PPP\$ GDP C. Knowledge Absorption 5.48 Royalty & license fees payments, % total trade 5.49 High-tech imports less re-imports, % total trade 5.50 Comm., comp. & info services imports, % total trade 5.51 FDI net inflows, % GDP
<u>Innovation Output Subindexes</u>
6th Pillar: Knowledge and Technology Outputs
A. Knowledge Creation 6.52 Domestic resident patent app/bn PPP\$ GDP 6.53 PCT resident patent app/bn PPP\$ GDP 6.54 Domestic res utility model app/bn PPP\$ GDP 6.55 Scientific & technical articles/bn PPP\$ GDP B. Knowledge Impact 6.56 Growth rate of PPP\$ GDP/worker, % 6.57 New businesses/th pop. 15-64 6.58 Computer software spending, % GDP 6.59 ISO 9001 quality certificates/bn PPP\$ GDP

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2015)
C. Knowledge Diffusion 6.60 Royalty & license fees receipts, % total trade 6.61 High-tech exports less re-exports, % total trade 6.62 Comm., comp.& info. Services exports, % total trade 6.63 FDI net outflows, % GDP
7th Pillar: Creative Outputs
A. Intangible Assets 7.64 Domestic res trademark app/bn PPP\$ GDP 7.65 Madrid trademark applications/bn PPP\$ GDP 7.66 ICTs & business model creation 7.67 ICTs & organizational models creation B. Creative Goods and Services 7.68 Cultural & creative services exports, % total trade 7.69 National feature films/mn pop. 15–69 7.70 Creative goods exports, % total trade C. Online Creativity 7.71 Generic TLDs/th pop. 15–69 7.72 Country-cod eTLDs/th pop.15–69 7.73 Wikipedia monthly edits/mn pop.15–69 7.74 Video uploads on YouTube/pop.15–69

The framework assumes that a country’s innovation capability is the consequence of an evolutionary learning process (Nelson, 1988; Nelson and Winter, 1982) which does not always lead to a single, consistent set of institutional conditions for innovation capability (Lundvall, 2007; Pustovrh and Jaklič, 2014). Rather, the interplay among some, but not all, of those institutional conditions determines how it manifests in different ways. Kthedhaouria and Thurik (2017) employed a method called Fuzzy-set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) developed by Ragin (2008) to analyze a sample of 133 countries and 74 indicators retrieved from the database of the Global Innovation Index 2012-2015 to identify three distinctive configurational conditions leading to high levels of national innovation capability. Configuration

1 shows that despite the lack of a supporting market condition, a country can reach a high level of innovation capability through building national institutions, developing human capital and research systems, improving infrastructures, and facilitating business. Configuration 2 shows that a country can also reach a high level of innovation capability without appropriate institutions through developing human capital and research systems, improving infrastructures, and facilitating business and market conditions. Configuration 3 shows that the combination of all five conditions is necessary for a country to reach a very high innovation capability.

High Innovation Capability Outcomes	Innovation Capability Condition				
	Institutions	Human Capital and Research	Infrastructure	Market Condition	Business Condition
Configuration 1	•	•	•		•
Configuration 2		•	•	•	•
Very High Innovation Capability Outcomes	Innovation Capability Condition				
	Institutions	Human Capital and Research	Infrastructure	Market Condition	Business Condition
Configuration 3	•	•	•	•	•

Configuration	High Innovation Capability Outcomes		Very High Innovation Capability Outcomes
	Configuration 1	Configuration 2	Configuration 3
Country			
Australia	•	•	•
Austria	•	•	•
Belgium	•	•	•
Canada	•	•	•
Denmark	•	•	•
Estonia	•		
Finland	•	•	•
France	•	•	•
Germany	•	•	•
Hong Kong	•	•	•
Ireland			•
Israel		•	
Japan	•	•	•
Korea		•	
Luxembourg	•		•

Configuration	High Innovation Capability Outcomes		Very High Innovation Capability Outcomes
Netherlands	●	●	●
New Zealand	●	●	●
Norway	●	●	●
Singapore	●	●	●
Sweden	●	●	●
Switzerland	●	●	●
United Kingdom	●		●
United States	●	●	●

Corruption

Corruption is defined as the abuse of entrusted power (or public office) for private gain. Control of corruption, a similar concept to corruption, refers to perceptions of the degree to which public power is used for personal benefit, including both small-scale and large-scale corruption, as well as the capture of the state by elites and private interests (Cieřlik and Goczek, 2018). Control of corruption measures levels to which different forms of corruption take place in a certain jurisdiction (Thomas, 2006; Rose-Ackerman and Palifka, 2018). While research on the impact of corruption itself on CBDC adoption is limited, Kacker and Sinha (2024) found that more corrupt countries were more likely to engage in the research and launched stage of CBDC adoption, where less corrupt countries were more likely to engage in the development and pilot stage of CBDC adoption. Another insight might be gleaned from understanding the relationship between corruption and economic growth that has been analyzed through the so-called “helping hand” and “grabbing hand” effects. Heling hand indicates that corruption might be an efficient lubricant in rigid economic regulatory and bureaucratic environments (Bjorvatn and Søreide, 2005). The grabbing hand claims that corruption in an economy mimics a grabbing hand that increases rent seeking costs and discourages economic growth (Bliss and di Tella, 1997). Therefore, it may be possible posit that corruption may strengthen or weaken the impact of the five national

innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructures, market sophistication, and business sophistication) on the adoption of a CBDC and the impact of their two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) on the adoption of a CBDC, respectively.

Research Model and Hypotheses

The main research question for the proposed study is, “Why do some countries have a higher likelihood of adopting a CBDC than others?” Specifically, this study intends to examine national system of innovation (NIS) characteristics as determinants of CBDC adoption by focusing on the five national innovation capability enablers and the two national innovation capability outcomes (Khedhaouria and Thurik, 2017). The study proposes four hypotheses:

- Hypothesis 1: Stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 1 is that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between a country’s national innovation capability enablers and its CBDC adoption.
- Hypothesis 2: Stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 2 is that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between a country’s national innovation capability outcomes and its CBDC adoption.
- Hypothesis 3: Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the adoption of a CBDC. The null

hypothesis for Hypothesis 3 is that the interaction between corruption and the national innovation capability enablers does not significantly predict the adoption of a CBDC.

- Hypothesis 4: Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and the adoption of a CBDC. The null hypothesis for Hypothesis 4 is that the interaction between corruption and the national innovation capability outcomes does not significantly predict the adoption of a CBDC.

Figure 11 A Research Model of CBDC Adoption

CHAPTER 3: METHODS

Research Design

My research question was “Why are some countries more likely than others to advance to higher stages of CBDC adoption?” In answering this question, I examined the extent to which the seven national system of innovation (NIS) characteristics—the five national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the two national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs)—might impact a country’s advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption.

I considered several research designs, including a case study design, a laboratory experimental design, a cross-sectional survey design, and an archival design. I determined that an archival research design is most appropriate for this study due to several reasons highlighted below (Bryman & Bell, 2015). First, it minimizes the occurrence of missing data. Second, it allows for the utilization of objective measures by using those two archival sources mentioned above, as opposed to perceptual measures. Third, it ensures a sufficient sample size primarily because I will utilize those archival data containing numerous observations. Both databases are widely used in business research because they provide reliable and comprehensive data. Lastly, an archival design is most cost-effective and time efficient.

A case study allows researchers to make direct observations and collect data in natural settings when they illuminate a particular situation, to get a close (i.e., in-depth and first-hand) understanding of it and is pertinent when the goal of research is to address either a descriptive question (*what* happened?) or an explanatory question (*how* or *why* did something happen?). An experimental design refers to how participants are allocated to the different conditions (or

independent variable groups) in an experiment and deliberately imposes a treatment on a group of objects or subjects in the interest of observing the response (Mcleod, 2007). Using an experimental design which involves human subjects in social science research was not a suitable choice. It was practically impossible to employ a case study design because it couldn't collect necessary data to meet the goal of the study. Further, since I expected to conduct this study for numerous countries, not just one or two, a case design requiring making direct observations at such countries would have posed significant challenges in terms of resource constraints and arrangements to conduct research. Additionally, I expected that using a survey design would provide less comprehensive data due to such problems as low response issues.

Data Gathering

To test the hypotheses, I gathered data from five archival sources—Central Digital Bank Currency (CBDC) Tracker (<https://cbdctracker.org>) to operationalize the dependent variable representing a country's CBDC adoption stage, [the Global Innovation Index \(GII\) database](#) maintained by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) to operationalize the independent variables, and finally the World Governance Indicators (WGI), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI) to operationalize the control variable.

CBDC Tracker. Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) Tracker (<https://cbdctracker.org>) is an open-source project aimed at providing a comprehensive information resource for world CBDC initiatives. Its main components are Dashboard, CBDC Information Card, Timelines and Time Slider, News Aggregator, Watchlist Tool (see Mikhalev et al., 2021 for detail). The current CBDC attributes list used by CBDC Tracker is presented below.

- **Country/Region:** The name of a country or a region where a certain CBDC project has been started.
- **Announcement Year:** The year a CBDC project was first announced.
- **Central Bank(s):** The name of a central bank or central banks responsible for a CBDC project.
- **Digital Currency:** The name of a digital currency (may be unknown for some projects).
- **Status:** The current (or historic) status of a CBDC:
 - *Cancelled:* Countries that cancelled or decommissioned a CBDC.
 - *Research:* Countries that published multiple research reports about CBDC and started experimenting.
 - *Pilot:* Countries piloting CBDC in a real environment with a limited number of parties.
 - *Development:* Countries that already launched a small-scale pilot but currently prepare their CBDC for a full-scale launch.
 - *Launched:* Countries that officially launched a CBDC.
- **Retail/Wholesale:** A CBDC can be either wholesale (e.g., for inter-bank transaction only) or retail (intended to be used by the end user).
- **Structure:** A CBDC can be stored either as a token or as an account.
- **Technology:** The name of a technological platform behind a CBDC.
- **Programmability:** Does a CBDC support programmable logic (e.g., smart contracts)?
- **Interoperability:** Does a CBDC support integration with other digital currencies?
- **Governance structure:** Who has rights to control a CBDC (a central bank, or consortium, etc)?

- Centralization: Is a CBDC based on centralized or decentralized principles?
- DLT / non-DLT: Is a CBDC built on top of distributed ledger technology (DLT)?
- Main motivation/goals of the CBDC: For what reasons has a certain central bank or government started a CBDC project?
- Remuneration: Is a CBDC interest-bearing or non-interest-bearing?
- International access: Does a CBDC allow itself to be accessed from outside a country it has been issued by?
- Caps / Limits: Are there any limits (e.g., cap on CBDC holdings) connected to a CBDC?
- Emission amount: The current amount of emission (if available).
- Offline payments: Does a CBDC support offline payments?
- Anonymity: Does a CBDC support anonymous transactions?
- Distribution: A distribution scheme or principles of a CBDC.
- Link to announcement: A URL of where a CBDC has been announced.
- Link to site of project: A URL of an official website of a CBDC (if available).
- Links to social networks: URLs of official social network pages of a CBDC (if available).
- Description: a free-form description of a CBDC.

When you open the CBDC Tracker website, the dashboard is what you see first. The main components of the Dashboard are:

- World map with colors showing the current CBDC status in each country
- Data table that supports sorting and controlling visible columns.
- Filters panel.
- Latest news.
- Time slider.

The data table is the main feature of the Dashboard where rows for each CBDC with configurable columns are presented below the World map. Some of the columns—such as Digital Currency, Country/Region, Central Bank(s), Announcement Year, Status, and Update Rate—are fixed and cannot be hidden. The Update Rate column is a graphical representation of a CBDC activity for the last 12 months. It is in a form of a bar chart where each bar represents the monthly activity (the amount of news plus number of updates for a CBDC).

Cancelled CBDC Projects (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Avant	Finland	Bank of Finland	1992	Retail
E-kroner	Denmark	Nationalbanken	2017	Retail
Dinero electrónico	Ecuador	Central Bank of Ecuador	2017	Retail
Kenya CBDC	Kenya	Central Bank of Kenya	2018	Retail

Cancelled CBDC Projects (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Curacao CBDC	Curacao	Central Bank of Curacao and Sint Maarten	2018	Retail
Digital Dollar	USA	US Federal Reserve	2020	Retail
Philippines CBDC	Philippines	The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas	2021	Retail
Project Orchid	Singapore	Monetary Authority of Singapore	2021	Retail
Fiji CBDC	Fiji	Reserve Bank of Fiji	2022	Retail

CBDC Projects in Proof of Concept Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Jasper	Canada	Bank of Canada	2016	Wholesale
DREX	Brazil	Central Bank of Brazil	2017	Wholesale
e-krona	Sweden	Sveriges Riksbank	2017	Retail
e-shekel	Israel	Bank of Israel	2017	Retail
e-hryvnia	Ukraine	National Bank of Ukraine	2017	Retail
Project Garuda	Indonesia	Bank Indonesia	2018	Wholesale
Digital Rupiah	Indonesia	Bank Indonesia	2018	Retail, Wholesale
Norway CBDC	Norway	Norges Bank	2019	Retail
e-HKD	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2019	Retail
United Arab Emirates CBDC	United Arab Emirates	United Arab Emirates Central Bank	2019	Retail
Inthanon-LionRock	Thailand	Bank of Thailand	2019	Wholesale

CBDC Projects in Proof of Concept Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Inthanon-LionRock	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2019	Wholesale
Jasper-Ubin	Canada	Bank of Canada	2019	Wholesale
Inthanon	Thailand	Bank of Thailand	2019	Wholesale
Jasper-Ubin	Singapore	Monetary Authority of Singapore	2019	Wholesale
New Zealand CBDC	New Zealand	Reserve Bank of New Zealand	2020	Retail
Thailand CBDC	Thailand	Bank of Thailand	2020	Retail
Project Hamilton	United States of America	US Federal Reserve	2020	Retail
South Korea CBDC	South Korea	Bank of Korea	2020	Retail
Project Atom	Australia	Reserve Bank of Australia	2020	Wholesale
e-MOP	Macau	Macau Government	2021	Retail
Digital yen	Japan	Bank of Japan	2021	Retail
Palau Stablecoin	Republic of Palau		2021	Others
Laos CBDC	Laos	Bank of the Lao PDR	2021	Retail
Agila	Philippines	The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas	2022	Wholesale
Digital Lari	Georgia	National Bank of Georgia	2022	Retail
Project Cedar Phase II x Project Ubin+	United States of America	US Federal Reserve	2022	Wholesale
Bokolo Cash	Solomon Islands	Central Bank of Solomon Islands	2023	Retail
Digital Som	Kyrgyzstan	National Bank of the Kyrgyz Republic	2024	Retail

CBDC Projects in Proof of Concept Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Qatar Wholesale CBDC	Qatar	Qatar Central Bank	2024	Wholesale

CBDC Projects in Pilot Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
e-CNY	China	People's Bank of China	2014	Retail
e-Peso	Uruguay	Central Bank of Uruguay	2014	Retail
Digital Lira	Turkey	Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey	2018	Retail
Digital Rial	Iran	Central Bank of Iran	2018	Retail
E-cedi	Ghana	The Bank of Ghana	2018	Retail
Digital Ruble	Russian Federation	Bank of Russia	2019	Retail
Aber	United Arab Emirates	United Arab Emirates Central Bank	2019	Wholesale
Aber	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority	2019	Wholesale
Digital Tenge	Kazakhstan	National Bank of Kazakhstan	2020	Retail, Wholesale
Digital Rupee	India	RBI	2020	Retail, Wholesale
Helvetia	Switzerland	Swiss National Bank	2020	Wholesale
Digital Won	South Korea	Bank of Korea	2020	Retail
Hungary CBDC	Hungary	Central Bank of Hungary (MNB)	2020	Retail
French Wholesale CBDC	France	Banque de France	2021	Wholesale
Project Prosperus	Tunisia	Central Bank of Tunisia	2021	Wholesale

CBDC Projects in Pilot Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Project Prosperus	France	Banque de France	2021	Wholesale
Wholesale Digital Euro	Euro Area	European Central Bank	2022	Wholesale
mBridge	United Arab Emirates	United Arab Emirates Central Bank	2022	Wholesale
mBridge	Thailand	Bank of Thailand	2022	Wholesale
mBridge	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority	2022	
mBridge	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2022	Wholesale
mBridge	China	People's Bank of China	2022	Wholesale
Project Venus	Luxembourg	Banque centrale du Luxembourg	2022	Wholesale
Project Venus	France	Banque de France	2022	Wholesale
Project Ubin+	Singapore	Monetary Authority of Singapore	2022	Wholesale
South Korea Wholesale CBDC	South Korea	Bank of Korea	2023	Wholesale
TIPS Hash-Link	Italy	Banca D'Italia	2024	Wholesale
Trigger Solution	Germany	Deutsche Bundesbank	2024	Wholesale

CBDC Projects Launched (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Sand Dollar	Bahamas	Central Bank of Bahamas	2017	Retail
ZiG	Zimbabwe	Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe	2021	Others
e-Naira	Nigeria	Central Bank of Nigeria	2021	Retail

CBDC Projects Launched (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
JAM-DEX	Jamaica	Bank of Jamaica	2023	Retail

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
RSCoin	United Kingdom	Bank of England	2015	Retail
Stella	Japan	Bank of Japan	2016	Others
Stella	Euro Area	European Central Bank	2016	Others
E-ringgit	Malaysia	Bank Negara Malaysia	2017	Retail
Digital Loonie	Canada	Bank of Canada	2017	Retail, Wholesale
DCash	Eastern Caribbean Economic and Currency Union (OECS/ECCU)	Eastern Caribbean Central Bank (ECCB)	2017	Retail
Palestine CBDC	Palestine	Palestine Monetary Authority	2017	Retail
Digital zloty	Poland	Narodowy Bank Polski (NBP)	2017	Retail
Digital Pound	United Kingdom	Bank of England	2018	Retail
Egypt CBDC	Egypt	Central Bank of Egypt (CBE)	2018	Retail
Digital Dinar	Bahrain	Central Bank of Bahrain (CBB)	2018	Retail
Rafkrona	Iceland	Central Bank of Iceland	2018	Retail
digital lilangeni	Eswatini	Central Bank of Eswatini	2019	Retail
Project Ensemble	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2019	Wholesale

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Rwanda CBDC	Rwanda	The National Bank of Rwanda	2019	Retail
South Africa CBDC	South Africa	South African Reserve Bank	2019	Retail
Chile CBDC	Chile	Central Bank of Chile	2019	Retail
Saudi Arabia Wholesale CBDC	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority	2019	Wholesale
Pakistan CBDC	Pakistan	State Bank of Pakistan	2019	Retail
Kuwait CBDC	Kuwait	Central Bank of Kuwait	2019	Retail
Khokha	South Africa	South African Reserve Bank	2019	Wholesale
Saudi Arabia Retail CBDC	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority	2019	Retail
e-franc	Switzerland	Swiss National Bank	2019	Retail
e-Dinar	Tunisia	Central Bank of Tunisia	2019	Retail
LionRock	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2019	Wholesale
Project Acacia	Australia	Reserve Bank of Australia	2020	Wholesale
eAUD	Australia	Reserve Bank of Australia	2020	Retail
Taiwan CBDC	Taiwan	The Central Bank of Taiwan	2020	Retail, Wholesale
Gourde Digitale	Haiti	La Banque de la Republique d'Haiti	2020	Retail
Lebanon CBDC	Lebanon	Lebanon's central bank	2020	Retail
Vietnam CBDC	Vietnam	State Bank of Vietnam	2021	Retail
Retail Digital Euro	Euro Area	European Central Bank	2021	Retail
e-Ariary	Madagascar	Banky Foiben'i Madagasikara	2021	Retail

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Peru CBDC	Peru	Central Reserve Bank of Peru	2021	Retail
digital Ngultrum	Bhutan	Royal Monetary Authority	2021	Retail, Wholesale
Honduras CBDC	Honduras	Central Bank of Honduras	2021	Retail
Tanzania CBDC	Tanzania	Bank of Tanzania	2021	Retail, Wholesale
Moneda digital del banco central (MDBC)	Mexico	Bank of Mexico (Banxico)	2021	Retail
Namibia CBDC	Namibia	Bank of Namibia	2021	Retail
Zimbabwe CBDC	Zimbabwe	Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe	2021	Retail
Trinidad and Tobago CBDC	Trinidad and Tobago	Central Bank of Trinidad and Tobago	2021	Retail
Jura	Switzerland	Swiss National Bank	2021	Wholesale
Paraguay CBDC	Paraguay	Central Bank of Paraguay	2021	Retail
Jura	France	Banque de France	2021	Wholesale
iQuetzal	Guatemala	Bank of Guatemala	2021	Retail
Costa Rica CBDC	Costa Rica	Banco Central de Costa Rica	2021	Retail
Vanuatu CBDC	Vanuatu	Reserve Bank of Vanuatu	2021	Retail
Tonga CBDC	Tonga	National Reserve Bank of Tonga (NRBT)	2021	Retail
DELPHI	Austria	Oesterreichische Nationalbank	2021	Wholesale
Morocco CBDC	Morocco	Bank-Al-Maghrib	2021	Retail
Czech Republic CBDC	Czech Republic	Czech National Bank	2021	Retail

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Dominican Republic CBDC	Dominican Republic	Banco Central de la República Dominicana	2022	Retail
Azerbaijan CBDC	Azerbaijan	Central Bank of Azerbaijan	2022	Retail
Spanish Wholesale CBDC	Spain	Banco de España	2022	Wholesale
Project Aurum	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2022	Retail
Sri Lanka CBDC	Sri Lanka	Central Bank of Sri Lanka	2022	Retail
Digital Peso	Argentina	Banco Central de la República Argentina	2022	Retail
Project Mariana	Switzerland	Swiss National Bank	2022	Wholesale
Project Mariana	Singapore	Monetary Authority of Singapore	2022	Wholesale
Sela	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2022	Retail
Project Mariana	France	Banque de France	2022	Wholesale
Project Cedar Phase II x Project Ubin+	Singapore	Monetary Authority of Singapore	2022	Wholesale
Algerian Digital Dinar	Algeria	Banque d'Algérie	2022	Retail
Mongolia CBDC	Mongolia	Bank of Mongolia	2022	Retail
Oman CBDC	Oman	Central Bank of Oman	2022	Retail
Project Icebreaker	Sweden	Sveriges Riksbank	2022	Retail
Project Icebreaker	Norway	Norges Bank	2022	Retail
Nepal CBDC	Nepal	The Nepal Rastra Bank	2022	Retail
Project Icebreaker	Israel	Bank of Israel	2022	Retail

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
EMCCA CBDC	Economic and Monetary Community of Central Africa (EMCCA)	Banque des États de l'Afrique Centrale	2022	Retail
Cote d'Ivoire CBDC	Cote d'Ivoire	Cote d'Ivoire	2022	Retail
Botswana CBDC	Botswana	Bank of Botswana	2022	Retail
Bangladesh CBDC	Bangladesh	Bangladesh Bank	2022	Retail
Sudan CBDC	Sudan	Central Bank of Sudan	2022	Retail
Malaysia CBDC	Malaysia	Bank Negara Malaysia	2022	Wholesale
Zambia CBDC	Zambia	The Bank of Zambia (BoZ)	2022	Retail
Yemen CBDC	Yemen	Central Bank of Yemen	2022	Retail
Uganda CBDC	Uganda	Bank of Uganda	2022	Retail, Wholesale
Qatar CBDC	Qatar	Qatar Central Bank	2022	Retail
Iraq CBDC	Iraq	Central Bank of Iraq	2022	Retail, Wholesale
Denmark CBDC	Denmark	Nationalbanken	2022	Wholesale
Jordan CBDC	Jordan	Central Bank of Jordan	2022	Retail
Solomon Islands CBDC	Solomon Islands	Central Bank of Solomon Islands	2022	Retail
Colombia CBDC	Colombia	Banco de la República	2023	Retail, Wholesale
Mauritania CBDC	Mauritania	Central Bank of Mauritania	2023	Retail
Digital Ruble	Belarus	Central Bank of Belarus	2023	Retail
Armenia CBDC	Armenia	Central Bank of Armenia	2023	Retail

CBDC Projects in Research Stage (as of February 2025)				
Digital Currency	Country / Region	Central Bank(s)	Announcement Year	Retail vs. Wholesale
Maldives CBDC	Maldives	Maldives Monetary Authority	2023	Retail
Sela	Israel	Bank of Israel	2023	Retail
Mauritius CBDC	Mauritius	The Bank of Mauritius	2023	Retail
Wholesale Digital Dollar	United States of America	US Federal Reserve	2023	Wholesale
Montenegro CBDC	Montenegro	Central Bank of Montenegro	2023	Retail
Cross-border Projects with Brazil & Thailand	Hong Kong	Hong Kong Monetary Authority	2024	Retail
Digital Florin	Aruba	Central Bank van Aruba	2024	Retail
Malawi CBDC	Malawi	Reserve Bank of Malawi	2024	Retail
Papua New Guinea CBDC	Papua New Guinea	Central Bank of Papua New Guinea	2024	Retail
Ethiopia CBDC	Ethiopia	National Bank of Ethiopia	2024	Retail

Global Innovation Index 2024. I collected the data for the independent variables from the Global Innovation Index (GII) database (<https://www.wipo.int/en/web/global-innovation-index>) maintained by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), a specialized agency of the United Nations. The GII was launched in 2007 by Professor Soumitra Dutta (then at INSEAD) and World Business, a British magazine, to aim at identifying and determining metrics and methods that could capture a picture of innovation in society that is as complete as possible. Until 2021 when WIPO became the sole editor of the GII, the index was co-published by WIPO in partnership with Cornell University, INSEAD and other organizations and institutions. Since

its inception in 2007 and now in its 17th edition, the GII has been one of the most popular references to measure the innovative performance of economies around the world (World Intellectual Property Organization, 2024).

The GII adopts a broad definition of innovation, which refers to “a new or improved product or process (or combination thereof) that differs significantly from the unit’s previous products or processes and that has been made available to potential users (product) or brought into use by the unit (process)” (OECD and Eurostat, 2018). The process of understanding and modeling the fundamentals of innovation at the national level and across the globe inevitably entails conceptual and practical challenges. Now in its 17th edition, the GII 2024 considers these conceptual challenges and deals with practical issues – related to data quality and methodological choices – by grouping economy-level data for 133 economies across 78 indicators into 21 sub-pillars (three sub-pillars per each pillar), seven pillars, two sub-indices and, finally, an overall index.

The overall GII ranking is based on two sub-indices—the Innovation Input Sub-Index built on five pillars and the Innovation Output Sub-Index built on two pillars. Five innovation input pillars capture elements of the national economy that enable and facilitate innovative activities: institutions (Pillar 1), human capital and research (Pillar 2), infrastructure (Pillar 3), market sophistication (Pillar 4), and business sophistication (Pillar 5). Two innovation output pillars capture actual evidence of innovation outcomes: knowledge and technology outputs (Pillar 6) and creative outputs (Pillar 7). The core idea behind this GII framework is that the basis for tomorrow's innovation outputs is laid by today's innovation inputs along with the accompanying efforts to build the science, innovation, and human capital base, and the related innovation environment. Each of the five innovation input pillars and two innovation output

pillars is divided into three sub-pillars, each of which is composed of individual indicators. Each sub-pillar is calculated by taking the weighted average of its individual indicators' scores, which are normalized to again produce scores between 0 and 100. Pillar scores are calculated using the weighted average of each pillar's sub-pillar scores. The GII framework considers both Innovation Input Sub-Index and Innovation Output Sub-Index as equally important in presenting a complete picture of innovation. Therefore, in determining the overall GII scores, the Output Sub-Index, although it has only two pillars, carries the same weight as the Input Sub-Index. Put differently, the Output Sub-Index—the pillars and indicators of knowledge and technology outputs (Pillar 6) and creative outputs (Pillar 7)—carries a disproportionately higher weight than the Input Sub-Index—those of institutions (Pillar 1), human capital and research (Pillar 2), infrastructure (Pillar 3), market sophistication (Pillar 4), and business sophistication (Pillar 5).

The two sub-indexes and the overall GII ranking are calculated as follows:

- Innovation Input Sub-Index is the simple average of the five innovation input pillar scores.
- The Innovation Output Sub-Index is the simple average of the two innovation output pillar scores.
- The overall GII score is the simple average of the Input and Output Sub-Indexes.

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2024)
INOVATION INPUT INDEX
1st Pillar: Institutions
<p><i>A. Institutional Environment</i> 1.1 Operational stability (political, legal or operational or security risk) for businesses 2023 1.2 Government effectiveness 2022</p> <p><i>B. Regulatory Environment</i> 1.3 Regulatory quality 2022</p>

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2024)
<p>1.4 Rule of law 2022</p> <p>C. Business Environment</p> <p>1.5 Political stability for doing business 2023</p> <p>1.6 Entrepreneurship policies and culture 2023</p>
2nd Pillar: Human Capital and Research
<p>A. Education</p> <p>2.7 Government expenditure on education (% of GDP) 2022</p> <p>2.8 Government funding per secondary pupil (% of GDP per capita) 2020</p> <p>2.9 School life expectancy, primary to tertiary education, both sexes (years) 2022</p> <p>2.10 PISA scales in reading, mathematics and science 2022</p> <p>2.11 Pupil-teacher ratio, secondary</p> <p>B. Tertiary Education</p> <p>2.12 School enrolment, tertiary (% gross) 2022</p> <p>2.13 Graduates from science, technology, engineering and mathematics programs (% of total tertiary graduates) 2021</p> <p>2.14 Tertiary inbound mobility rate (%) 2022</p> <p>C. Research and Development (R&D)</p> <p>2.15 Researchers, full-time equivalent (FTE) (per million population) 2022</p> <p>2.16 Gross expenditure on R&D (% of GDP) 2022</p> <p>2.17 Global corporate R & D investors, top 3, mn USD – Average expenditure of a country’s top three global companies on R & D, million USD 2023</p> <p>2.18 QS university ranking, top 3 – Average score of the top three universities according to the QS world university ranking 2023</p>
3rd Pillar: Infrastructure
<p>A. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)</p> <p>3.19 ICT access 2022</p> <p>3.20 ICT use 2022</p> <p>3.21 Government's online service 2022</p> <p>3.22 E-participation 2022</p> <p>B. General Infrastructure</p> <p>3.23 Electricity output (GWh per million population) 2023</p> <p>3.24 Logistic performance 2023</p> <p>3.25 Gross capital formation (% of GDP, three-year average) 2023</p> <p>C. Ecological Sustainability</p> <p>3.26 GDP per total energy supply (per thousand 2015 PPP\$ GDP) 2021</p>

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2024)
<p>3.27 Low-carbon energy use, % – the share of a country’s total primary energy consumption that is from low-carbon intensive sources) 2022</p> <p>3.28 ISO14001 Environment management systems – Number of certificates issued (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2022</p>
<p>4th Pillar: Market Sophistication</p>
<p><i>A. Credit</i></p> <p>4.29 Finance for startups and scaleups 2023</p> <p>4.30 Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP) 2022</p> <p>4.31 Loans from all microfinance institutions (% of GDP) 2022</p> <p><i>B. Investment</i></p> <p>4.32 Market capitalization, % GDP – Market capitalization of listed domestic companies (% of GDP, three-year average) 2022</p> <p>4.33 Venture capital (VC) investors, deals/bn PPP\$ GDP – Number of VC deals invested in (per billion PPP\$ GDP, three-year average) 2023</p> <p>4.34 VC recipients, deals/bn PPP\$ GDP – Number of venture capital deals received (per billion PPP\$ GDP, three-year average) 2023</p> <p>4.35 VC received, value, % GDP – Total value of venture capital received (% of GDP, three-year average) 2023</p> <p><i>C. Trade, Diversification and Market Scale</i></p> <p>4.36 Tariff rate, applied, weighted average, all products (%) 2022</p> <p>4.37 Domestic industry diversification – The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index based on manufacturing output) 2023</p> <p>4.38 Domestic market scale measured by GDP based on the PPP valuation of country GDP, in current international dollars (billions) 2023</p>
<p>5th Pillar: Business Sophistication</p>
<p><i>A. Knowledge Workers</i></p> <p>5.39 Employment in knowledge-intensive services (% of workforce, 15+ years old) 2022</p> <p>5.40 Firms offering formal training (% of firms) 2023</p> <p>5.41 GERD (Gross expenditure on R & D) performed by business (% of GDP) 2023</p> <p>5.42 GERD financed by business (% of GERD) 2021</p> <p>5.43 Females employed with advanced degrees (% total employed, 25+ years old) 2023</p> <p><i>B. Innovation Linkages</i></p> <p>5.44 Public-private co-authored research publications (% of total research publications, five-year average) 2023</p> <p>5.45 University-industry R & D collaboration 2023</p> <p>5.46 State of cluster development 2023</p> <p>5.47 Joint venture/strategic alliance deals (per billion PPP\$ GDP, three-year average) 2023</p>

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2024)
<p>5.48 Patent families filed in at least two offices (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2020</p> <p>C. Knowledge Absorption</p> <p>5.49 Intellectual property payments (% of total trade, three-year average) 2022</p> <p>5.50 High-tech imports (% of total trade) 2022</p> <p>5.51 Telecommunications, computer and information service imports (% of total trade) 2022</p> <p>5.52 FDI net inflows, (% of GDP, three-year average) 2022</p> <p>5.53 Research talent – Research in business enterprise (%) 2022</p>
INOVATION OUTPUT INDEX
6th Pillar: Knowledge and Technology Outputs
<p>A. Knowledge Creation</p> <p>6.54 Patents by origin – Number of resident patent applications at a given national or regional patent office (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2022</p> <p>6.55 PCT patents by origin – Number of Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) applications (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2023</p> <p>6.56 Utility models by origin – Number of resident utility model application filed at the national patent office (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2022</p> <p>6.57 Number of scientific and technical journal articles (per billion PPP\$ GDP) 2023</p> <p>6.58 Citable documents H-index – The economy’s number of published articles (H) that have received at least H citations) 2023</p> <p>B. Knowledge Impact</p> <p>6.59 Labor productivity growth – Growth rate of GDP per person employed (% , five-year average) 2023</p> <p>6.60 Unicorn valuable – Combined valuation of a country’s unicorns (% of GDP) 2024</p> <p>6.61 Total computer software spending (% of GDP) 2023</p> <p>6.62 High-tech & medium high-tech manufacturing (% of total manufacturing output) 2021</p> <p>C. Knowledge Diffusion</p> <p>6.63 Intellectual property receipts – Charges for use of intellectual property, i.e., receipts (% total trade, three-year average) 2022</p> <p>6.64 Production and export complexity – The Economic Complexity Index 2021</p> <p>6.65 High-tech exports (% of total trade) 2022</p> <p>6.66 ICT service exports (% of total trade) 2022</p> <p>6.67 ISO 9000 quality – Number of ISO 9000 certificates issued per billion PPP\$ GDP 2023</p>
7th Pillar: Creative Outputs
<p>A. Intangible Assets</p> <p>7.68 Intangible asset intensity, top 15, % – Intangible asset value a percentage of the firm’s total value, average of the top 15 firms 2023</p>

Structure of the Global Innovation Index (2024)

7.69 Trademarks by origin – Number of classes in resident applications issued at a given national or regional office (per billion PPP\$ GDP) | 2022

7.70 Global brand value, top 5,000, % GDP – Global brand value of the top 5,000 (% of GDP) | 2024

7.71 Industrial designs by origin – Number of designs contained in resident industrial design applications filed at a given national or regional office (per billion PPP\$ GDP) | 2022

B. Creative Goods and Services

7.72 Cultural and creative services exports (% of total trade) | 2022

7.73 National feature films – Number of national feature files produced (per million population, 15-69 years old) | 2023

7.74 Entertainment and media market/th pop. 16-59 – Global telecom and entertainment & media outlook (per thousand population, 15-69 years old) | 2023

7.75 Creative goods exports (% of total trade) | 2022

C. Online Creativity

7.76 Generic top-level domains (TLDs) and country-code TLDs (per thousand population, 15-69 years old) | 2023

7.77 Github commits pushes received and sent (per million population, 15-69 years old) | 2023

7.78 Mobile app creation – Global downloads of mobile apps (per billion PPP\$ GDP, two-year average) | 2023

Figure 12 Global Innovation Index Rankings (2024)

GII rank	Economy	Score	Income group rank	Region rank	GII rank	Economy	Score	Income group rank	Region rank
1	Switzerland	67.5	1	1	68	Republic of Moldova	28.7	17	36
2	Sweden	64.5	2	2	69	South Africa	28.3	18	2
3	United States of America	62.4	3	1	70	Costa Rica	28.3	18	6
4	Singapore	61.2	4	1	71	Kuwait	28.1	45	10
5	United Kingdom	61.0	5	3	72	Bahrain	27.6	46	11
6	Republic of Korea	60.9	6	2	73	Jordan	27.5	8	12
7	Finland	59.4	7	4	74	Oman	27.1	47	13
8	Netherlands (Kingdom of the)	58.8	8	5	75	Peru	26.7	20	7
9	Germany	58.1	9	6	76	Argentina	26.4	21	8
10	Denmark	57.1	10	7	77	Barbados	26.1	48	9
11	China	56.3	1	3	78	Kazakhstan	25.7	22	3
12	France	55.4	11	8	79	Jamaica	25.7	22	10
13	Japan	54.1	12	4	80	Bosnia and Herzegovina	25.5	24	37
14	Canada	52.9	13	2	81	Tunisia	25.4	9	14
15	Israel	52.7	14	1	82	Panama	24.7	49	11
16	Estonia	52.3	15	9	83	Uzbekistan	24.7	10	4
17	Austria	50.3	16	10	84	Albania	24.5	25	38
18	Hong Kong, China	50.1	17	5	85	Belarus	24.2	26	39
19	Ireland	50.0	18	11	86	Egypt	23.7	11	15
20	Luxembourg	49.1	19	12	87	Botswana	23.1	27	3
21	Norway	49.1	19	12	88	Brunei Darussalam	22.8	50	14
22	Iceland	48.5	21	14	89	Sri Lanka	22.6	12	5
23	Australia	48.1	22	6	90	Cabo Verde	22.3	13	4
24	Belgium	47.7	23	15	91	Pakistan	22.0	14	6
25	New Zealand	45.9	24	7	92	Senegal	22.0	14	5
26	Italy	45.3	25	16	93	Paraguay	21.9	28	12
27	Cyprus	45.1	26	2	94	Lebanon	21.5	16	16
28	Spain	44.9	27	17	95	Azerbaijan	21.3	29	17
29	Malta	44.8	28	18	96	Kenya	21.0	17	6
30	Czech Republic	44.0	29	19	97	Dominican Republic	20.8	30	13
31	Portugal	43.7	30	20	98	El Salvador	20.6	31	14
32	United Arab Emirates	42.8	31	3	99	Kyrgyzstan	20.4	18	7
33	Malaysia	40.5	2	8	100	Bolivia (Plurinational State of)	20.2	19	15
34	Slovenia	40.2	32	21	101	Ghana	20.0	20	7
35	Lithuania	40.1	33	22	102	Namibia	20.0	32	7
36	Hungary	39.6	34	23	103	Cambodia	19.9	21	15
37	Türkiye	39.0	3	4	104	Rwanda	19.7	1	9
38	Bulgaria	38.5	4	24	105	Ecuador	19.3	33	16
39	India	38.3	1	1	106	Bangladesh	19.1	22	8
40	Poland	37.0	35	25	107	Tajikistan	18.6	23	9
41	Thailand	36.9	5	9	108	Trinidad and Tobago	18.4	51	17
42	Latvia	36.4	36	26	109	Nepal	18.1	24	10
43	Croatia	36.3	37	27	110	Madagascar	17.9	2	10
44	Viet Nam	36.2	2	10	111	Lao People's Democratic Republic	17.8	25	16
45	Greece	36.2	38	28	112	Côte d'Ivoire	17.5	26	11
46	Slovakia	34.3	39	29	113	Nigeria	17.1	27	12
47	Saudi Arabia	33.9	40	5	114	Honduras	16.7	28	18
48	Romania	33.4	41	30	115	Algeria	16.2	29	18
49	Qatar	32.9	42	6	116	Zambia	15.7	30	13
50	Brazil	32.7	6	1	117	Togo	15.6	3	14
51	Chile	32.6	43	2	118	Zimbabwe	15.6	31	14
52	Serbia	32.3	7	31	119	Benin	15.4	32	16
53	Philippines	31.1	3	11	120	United Republic of Tanzania	15.3	33	17
54	Indonesia	30.6	8	12	121	Uganda	14.9	4	18
55	Mauritius	30.6	8	1	122	Guatemala	14.6	34	19
56	Mexico	30.4	10	3	123	Cameroon	14.4	34	19
57	Georgia	30.4	10	7	124	Nicaragua	14.0	35	20
58	North Macedonia	29.9	12	32	125	Myanmar	13.8	36	17
59	Russian Federation	29.7	13	33	126	Mauritania	13.2	37	20
60	Ukraine	29.5	4	34	127	Burundi	13.2	5	20
61	Colombia	29.2	14	4	128	Mozambique	13.1	6	22
62	Uruguay	29.1	44	5	129	Burkina Faso	12.8	7	23
63	Armenia	29.0	15	8	130	Ethiopia	12.3	8	24
64	Iran (Islamic Republic of)	28.9	5	2	131	Mali	11.8	9	25
65	Montenegro	28.9	16	35	132	Niger	11.2	10	26
66	Morocco	28.8	6	9	133	Angola	10.2	38	27
67	Mongolia	28.7	7	13					

High-income	Lower middle-income	Europe	South East Asia, East Asia, and Oceania	Sub-Saharan Africa
Upper middle-income	Low-income	Northern America	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Central and Southern Asia
		Latin America and the Caribbean		

Figure 13 Global Innovation Index Overall Ranking by Pillar (2024)

Economy	Overall GII	Institutions	Human capital and research	Infra-structure	Market sophistication	Business sophistication	Knowledge and technology outputs	Creative outputs
Switzerland	1	3	4	7	5	4	1	3
Sweden	2	16	3	1	9	1	2	6
United States	3	17	12	30	1	2	4	8
Singapore	4	1	2	11	7	3	9	19
United Kingdom	5	26	7	18	3	14	5	3
Republic of Korea	6	24	1	9	15	5	10	2
Finland	7	4	6	2	11	8	6	17
Netherlands (Kingdom of the)	8	9	14	25	14	7	8	7
Germany	9	19	5	27	13	18	11	5
Denmark	10	2	9	8	21	12	13	10
China	11	44	22	5	16	11	3	14
France	12	29	16	19	10	17	16	4
Japan	13	23	19	13	8	6	12	22
Canada	14	14	11	21	4	13	20	26
Israel	15	34	18	41	12	9	7	30
Estonia	16	12	31	6	6	27	21	15
Austria	17	18	8	10	32	23	18	24
Hong Kong, China	18	8	15	16	2	25	58	12
Ireland	19	11	25	20	48	16	14	28
Luxembourg	20	6	28	93	30	10	36	9
Norway	21	6	20	4	31	22	26	26
Iceland	22	13	26	3	22	21	37	21
Australia	23	15	10	15	29	26	28	29
Belgium	24	21	13	44	46	15	15	36
New Zealand	25	7	23	12	34	20	45	33
Italy	26	55	50	26	38	24	10	18
Cyprus	27	46	46	45	41	29	23	19
Spain	28	49	27	14	33	31	24	23
Malta	29	39	35	37	42	19	48	11
Czech Republic	30	30	32	24	75	30	17	33
Portugal	31	37	21	46	36	33	33	20
United Arab Emirates	32	10	17	17	26	24	56	40
Malaysia	33	27	38	52	18	36	35	49
Slovenia	34	41	24	26	62	32	27	48
Lithuania	35	22	44	38	28	38	29	55
Hungary	36	53	34	35	60	28	25	44
Turkiye	37	100	40	40	37	48	43	16
Bulgaria	38	83	62	22	50	44	39	27
India	39	54	51	72	23	58	22	43
Poland	40	73	36	51	61	35	47	35
Thailand	41	74	71	50	25	41	39	38
Latvia	42	42	45	33	53	40	51	39
Croatia	43	68	41	23	54	54	32	50
Viet Nam	44	58	73	56	43	46	44	34
Greece	45	57	29	42	66	65	40	41
Slovakia	46	63	52	47	68	43	31	58
Saudi Arabia	47	35	33	49	27	79	68	67
Romania	48	81	70	32	67	47	38	56
Qatar	49	20	48	39	59	68	82	61
Brazil	50	103	57	55	47	39	50	42
Chile	51	48	58	54	44	51	65	59
Serbia	52	67	50	22	40	63	41	85
Philippines	53	65	84	85	77	37	42	60
Indonesia	54	40	90	67	35	78	73	65
Mauritius	55	33	69	87	24	69	91	62
Mexico	56	106	63	71	56	56	55	47
Georgia	57	32	60	74	64	55	72	77
North Macedonia	58	75	77	43	69	52	53	72
Russian Federation	59	126	39	76	57	53	52	53
Ukraine	60	107	54	82	85	45	34	68
Colombia	61	80	87	64	70	42	61	66
Uruguay	62	31	83	48	94	70	69	81
Armenia	63	77	89	79	83	85	60	46
Iran (Islamic Republic of)	64	133	64	95	17	110	49	52
Montenegro	65	86	61	57	52	59	74	70
Morocco	66	78	81	88	82	122	70	37
Mongolia	67	93	86	73	106	61	86	53
Republic of Moldova	68	90	68	89	63	105	64	51

Economy	Overall GII	Institutions	Human capital and research	Infra-structure	Market sophistication	Business sophistication	Knowledge and technology outputs	Creative outputs
South Africa	69	91	79	75	49	57	63	63
Costa Rica	70	47	82	59	87	50	59	86
Kuwait	71	66	53	60	76	120	67	69
Bahrain	72	28	75	36	80	83	83	95
Jordan	73	52	85	90	55	72	76	76
Oman	74	43	66	63	73	86	87	82
Peru	75	85	49	62	51	77	95	74
Argentina	76	123	55	77	97	60	77	54
Barbados	77	50	80	108	107	49	57	89
Kazakhstan	78	76	65	68	86	66	85	83
Jamaica	79	59	98	104	110	75	94	45
Bosnia and Herzegovina	80	110	72	69	29	124	71	94
Tunisia	81	102	47	107	84	119	54	73
Panama	82	82	99	58	95	112	90	64
Uzbekistan	83	62	93	70	78	71	78	103
Albania	84	60	101	31	91	64	89	99
Belarus	85	132	43	84	98	81	46	92
Egypt	86	94	96	92	74	103	81	78
Botswana	87	36	74	97	79	62	112	108
Brunei Darussalam	88	25	56	65	105	82	115	124
Sri Lanka	89	101	110	66	100	87	79	84
Cabo Verde	90	45	102	34	103	89	100	111
Pakistan	91	118	119	125	90	73	66	71
Senegal	92	70	106	81	72	123	62	112
Paraguay	93	96	115	61	88	102	113	75
Lebanon	94	128	59	116	45	80	80	93
Azerbaijan	95	51	94	102	114	67	103	96
Kenya	96	87	118	106	101	93	75	103
Dominican Republic	97	61	104	83	116	97	105	91
El Salvador	98	99	109	103	89	90	101	80
Kyrgyzstan	99	110	42	28	81	112	107	104
Bolivia (Plurinational State of)	100	127	67	124	119	84	120	102
Ghana	101	71	113	105	129	76	116	79
Namibia	102	56	91	113	93	92	122	105
Cambodia	103	89	111	103	99	124	98	106
Rwanda	104	38	95	93	117	113	105	114
Ecuador	105	109	100	80	113	94	96	98
Bangladesh	106	108	128	86	92	126	92	88
Tajikistan	107	104	92	109	96	101	84	115
Trinidad and Tobago	108	72	37	110	128	111	104	121
Nepal	109	111	130	100	65	116	110	97
Madagascar	110	124	108	133	99	130	124	57
Lao People's Democratic Republic	111	88	121	96	58	106	108	123
Côte d'Ivoire	112	69	129	98	126	98	128	100
Nigeria	113	125	78	127	121	107	121	87
Honduras	114	122	88	112	100	100	99	118
Algeria	115	95	76	94	132	114	125	109
Zambia	116	92	97	91	112	95	131	131
Togo	117	112	116	126	108	121	111	107
Zimbabwe	118	130	127	128	119	91	97	90
Benin	119	64	112	118	123	108	117	129
United Republic of Tanzania	120	79	132	111	120	118	129	113
Uganda	121	84	123	120	124	129	102	116
Guatemala	122	114	126	117	111	88	109	125
Cameroon	123	98	114	129	130	74	119	117
Nicaragua	124	129	117	114	71	99	118	130
Myanmar	125	131	107	115	102	132	93	118
Mauritania	126	97	120	122	131	109	127	127
Burundi	127	115	105	119	118	122	132	120
Mozambique	128	121	122	99	134	127	130	128
Burkina Faso	129	105	103	132	115	131	134	126
Ethiopia	130	117	133	123	133	128	88	122
Mali	131	113	124	121	122	96	123	133
Niger	132	116	131	130	125	115	126	132
Angola	133	120	125	121	127	133	133	119

Legend: Dark green = 4th quartile (best performers, ranks 1st to 33rd); Light green = 3rd quartile (ranks 34th to 66th); Light orange = 2nd quartile (ranks 67th to 99th); Dark orange = 1st quartile (ranks 100th to 133th).
 Source: Global Innovation Index Database, WIPO, 2024.

Figure 14 Global Innovation Index 2024: Correlations between Sub-pillars and Pillars

Subpillar	Pillars						
	1. Institutions	2. Human capital and research	3. Infra-structure	4. Market sophistication	5. Business sophistication	6. Knowledge and technology outputs	7. Creative outputs
1.1 Institutional environment	0.96	0.75	0.8	0.64	0.78	0.67	0.69
1.2 Regulatory environment	0.94	0.79	0.81	0.67	0.82	0.72	0.74
1.3 Business environment	0.81	0.38	0.41	0.33	0.47	0.34	0.29
2.1 Education	0.54	0.8	0.63	0.58	0.64	0.6	0.62
2.2 Tertiary education	0.55	0.81	0.64	0.58	0.58	0.56	0.59
2.3 Research and development	0.69	0.89	0.74	0.8	0.91	0.9	0.84
3.1 Information and communication technologies	0.69	0.8	0.89	0.72	0.73	0.71	0.78
3.2 General infrastructure	0.64	0.58	0.74	0.51	0.58	0.55	0.5
3.3 Ecological sustainability	0.37	0.4	0.66	0.37	0.49	0.5	0.47
4.1 Credit	0.58	0.68	0.6	0.85	0.65	0.62	0.66
4.2 Investment	0.58	0.61	0.51	0.8	0.66	0.62	0.64
4.3 Trade, diversification, and market scale	0.41	0.67	0.67	0.75	0.63	0.7	0.68
5.1 Knowledge workers	0.66	0.86	0.77	0.71	0.93	0.83	0.8
5.2 Innovation linkages	0.82	0.78	0.7	0.73	0.9	0.81	0.76
5.3 Knowledge absorption	0.61	0.72	0.69	0.68	0.89	0.8	0.78
6.1 Knowledge creation	0.6	0.83	0.68	0.72	0.86	0.91	0.82
6.2 Knowledge impact	0.6	0.72	0.68	0.74	0.77	0.88	0.73
6.3 Knowledge diffusion	0.55	0.73	0.73	0.66	0.78	0.91	0.76
7.1 Intangible assets	0.45	0.67	0.61	0.66	0.67	0.7	0.91
7.2 Creative goods and services	0.66	0.73	0.74	0.71	0.82	0.79	0.8
7.3 Online creativity	0.69	0.8	0.74	0.7	0.83	0.79	0.81

Corruption Indexes. I collected data to operationalize corruption—which is the moderating variable—from three different corruption databases: The World Governance Indicators (WGI), The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI).

The World Governance Indicators (WGI). WGI report on six broad dimensions of governance in a sample of 214 countries and territories over the period 1996-2023. The six dimensions of governance include voice and accountability, regulatory quality, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, rule of law, government effectiveness, and control of corruption (see Kaufman and Kraay, 2024 for detail). The control of corruption dimension captures perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as “capture” of the state by elites and private interests. WGI do not use data from the Transnational International Corruption Perceptions Index because it itself is a compilation of existing data sources, in the same way the WGI are, and does not involve new data collection. The control of corruption dimension ranges from -2.5 to +2.5, where the higher the index is, the less the corruption is indicated. Therefore, I measured corruption using WGI’s country corruptions scores which range from -2.5 to + 2.5.

Countries are evaluated on the following factors:

- The prevalence of grand corruption and petty corruption at all levels of government;
- The effect of corruption on the “attractiveness” of a country as a place to do business;
- The frequency of “irregular payments” associated with import and export permits, public contracts, public utilities, tax assessments, and judicial decisions;
- Nepotism, cronyism and patronage in the civil service;
- The estimated cost of bribery as a share of a company’s annual sales;

- The perceived involvement of elected officials, border officials, tax officials, judges, and magistrates in corruption;
- The strength and effectiveness of a government's anti-corruption laws, policies, and institutions;
- The extent to which:
 - processes are put in place for accountability and transparency in decision-making and disclosure of information at the local level;
 - government authorities monitor the prevalence of corruption and implement sanctions transparently;
 - conflict of interest and ethics rules for public servants are observed and enforced;
 - the income and asset declarations of public officials are subject to verification and open to public and media scrutiny;
 - senior government officials are immune from prosecution under the law for malfeasance;
 - the government provides victims of corruption with adequate mechanisms to pursue their rights;
 - the tax administrator implements effective internal audit systems to ensure the accountability of tax collection;
 - the executive budget-making process is comprehensive and transparent and subject to meaningful legislative review and scrutiny;
 - the government ensures transparency, open-bidding, and effective competition in the awarding of government contracts;

- there are legal and functional protections for whistleblowers, anti-corruption activists, and investigators;
- allegations of corruption at the national and local level are thoroughly investigated and prosecuted without prejudice;
- government is free from excessive bureaucratic regulations, registration requirements, and/or other controls that increase opportunities for corruption;
- citizens have a legal right to information about government operations and can obtain government documents at a nominal cost.

The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI). CPI, which has been published annually by the non-governmental organization Transparency International since 1995, is a composite indicator to measure perceptions by business executives and country experts of the level of corruption in the public sector. The index considers 13 different surveys and assessments from 12 different institutions, including bribery, division of public funds, use of public office for private gain, nepotism in the civil service, and state capture. The 12 institutions include:

- [African Development Bank](#) (based in Ivory Coast)
- [Bertelsmann Foundation](#) (based in Germany)
- [Economist Intelligence Unit](#) (based in the UK)
- [Freedom House](#) (based in the US)
- [Global Insight](#) (based in the US)
- [International Institute for Management Development](#) (based in Switzerland)
- Political and Economic Risk Consultancy (based in Hong Kong)
- The PRS Group, Inc. (based in the US)
- [World Bank](#)

- [World Economic Forum](#)
- [World Justice Project](#) (based in the US)

Some of the sources pertain to the mechanisms available to prevent corruption in a country, such as the government's ability to enforce integrity mechanisms, the effective prosecution of corrupt officials, red tape and excessive bureaucratic burden, the existence of adequate laws on finance disclosure, conflict of interest prevention and access to information, and legal protection for whistleblowers, journalists and investigators. Countries need to be evaluated by at least three sources to appear in the CPI. Each of the sources included in the CPI is standardized to allow for the aggregation into the CPI score. The standardization converts all the data points to a scale of 0-100 where a 0 represents the highest level of perceived corruption, and 100 the lowest level of corruption. In the next step, the mean and standard deviation for each data sources based on data from the baseline year are calculated. Subsequently, a standardized z score is calculated with an average centered around 0 and a standard deviation of 1 for each source from each country. Finally, these scores are converted back to a 0-100 scale with a mean of approximately 45 and a standard deviation of 20. Scores below 0 are set at 0, and scores exceeding 100 are capped at 100 to ensure consistent comparability across years since 2012. Therefore, I measured corruption using CPI's country scores which range from 0 to 100.

Figure 15 Corruption Perceptions Index 2024

The *Global Corruption Index (GCI)*. The GCI which covers 196 countries and territories measures the corruption risk exposure deriving from both the public and private sectors. It also includes issues related to white collar crimes and more specifically to money-laundering and terrorism financing. It relies on numerous organizations including the UN, the OECD, the World Bank, the FATF, Transparency International, the Global Initiative, the World Justice Project Organization, the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU), the Basel Institute on Governance, the

International Budget Partnership (IPB), and the World Economic Forum (WEF) for their provision of raw data. Based on as many as 42 internationally recognized variables, it encompasses two sub-indexes—corruption and white-collar crimes—for both a global risk overview and a more nuanced risk assessment. The four indicators that are considered to measure corruption include (1) the ratification status of key conventions (OECD, UN), 15%; (2) the level of perceived public corruption (Transparency International’s Corruption Index, World Bank data, World Justice Project Organization data), 25.5%; (3) the reported experience of public and private corruption (Transparency International’s Global Corruption, Barometer, World Bank’s Enterprise Survey), 17%; and (4) a selection of country characteristics closely linked to corruption, 42.5%. Country characteristics are meant to capture prevention mechanisms, related effects, causal effects and consequential effects, with the objective of unearthing latent corruption information. This indicator aggregates results related to 4 different indicators: (1) citizen’s voice and transparency; (2) government functioning and effectiveness; (3) legal context; and (4) political context. The remaining weight (30%) is dedicated to white-collar crimes, a measure based on the Basel Institute’s AML Index and a set of white-collar crime indicators. Country scores are presented on a 0-100 scale, where 0 corresponds to the lowest risk and 100 to the highest risk. Therefore, I measured corruption using GCI’s country corruption scores which range from 0 to 100.

Figure 16 Global Corruption Index 2023

Sample

I used the CBDC Tracker as a sample framework, like in previous CBDC studies. All the CBDC initiatives as of February 2025 were available on the CBDC Tracker. I created a data set combining the five archival sources—the CBDC Tracker, the Global Innovation Index (GII), the World Governance Indicators (WGI), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI). My sample consisted of 110 CBDC initiatives: 69 at research stage, 19 at development stage, 19 at the pilot stage and 3 at the launched stage. Although the total number of CBDC initiatives as of May 2025 was 127, the sample was reduced to 110 because the CBDC initiatives pursued by countries (or economies) that did not have the national innovation capability scores or corruption scores were excluded from the analysis. Those countries (or economies) were Bhutan, Aruba, Bahamas, Eswatini, Haiti, Macau, Maldives, Palau, Palestine, Qatar, Solomon Islands Taiwan, Tanzania, Tonga, and Vanuatu.

Measurement

Dependent variable: CBDC adoption stage. The dependent variable of the study was a country's CBDC adoption stage. The CBDC Tracker (<https://cbdctracker.org>) is a useful resource as it categorizes the current (and historic) status of a CBDC using five stages of development. For this study, I assigned a value of 1 to *research*, a value of 2 to *proof of concept (development)*, a value of 3 to *pilot*, and a value of 4 to *launched* (Auer et al., 2021; Le et al., 2023) to operationalize a country's CBDC adoption stage. I excluded cancelled CBDC initiatives because my study was not designed to examine why countries canceled CBDC projects.

Independent variables: National innovation capability enablers and outcomes. The independent variables of the study were the five conditions of national innovation capability inputs (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and

business sophistication) and the two outcomes of national innovation capability outputs (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs). To operationalize these seven independent variables, I utilized the seven corresponding pillars within the Global Innovation Index (GII).

The GII is a composite index that is comprised of two sub-indexes—innovation input index and innovation output index. The innovation input sub-index measures the elements that enable and facilitate innovation, encompassing five pillars: institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication. The innovation output sub-index measures the outcomes of innovative activities within a country, including two pillars: knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs. For each pillar, country scores range from 0 (lowest) to 100 (highest) in terms of national innovation inputs or outputs. As such, all the independent variables will be operationalized as continuous variables. The moderator variable of the study is corruption. To operationalize this variable, I employed three corruption indexes—the control of corruption indicator within the World Governance Indicators ranging from -2.5 (highest corruption) to 2.5 (lowest corruption), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) ranging from 0 (highest corruption) to 100 (lowest corruption), and the Global Corruption Index (GCI) ranging from 0 (lowest corruption) to 100 (highest corruption)

Independent Variable	Operationalization using GII
Innovation capability enabler 1: institutions	Pillar 1: Institutions scored on a 0-100 scale
Innovation capability enabler 2: human capital and research	Pillar 2: Human research and capital scored on a 0-100 scale
Innovation capability enabler 3: infrastructure	Pillar 3: Infrastructure scored on a 0-100 scale

Independent Variable	Operationalization using GII
Innovation capability enabler 4: market sophistication	Pillar 4: Market sophistication scored on a 0-100 scale
Innovation capability enabler 5: business sophistication	Pillar 5: Business sophistication scored on a 0-100 scale
Innovation capability outcome 1: knowledge and technology outputs	Pillar 6: Knowledge and technology outputs scored on a 0-100 scale
Innovation capability outcome 2: creative outputs	Pillar 6: Creative outputs scored on a 0-100 scale

Moderator variable: corruption. The moderator variable of the study was a country's corruption level. Three different corruption indexes presented below were used to operationalize the moderator variable.

Corruption Index	Description
The control of corruption index within the world Governance Indicators (WGI)	Country scores range from -2.5 to +2.5, where -2.5 corresponds to the lowest control of corruption and 2.5 to the highest control of corruption.
The Corruption Perception Index (CPI)	Country scores range from 0 to 100, where 0 corresponds to the highest level of corruption and 100 to the lowest level of corruption.
The Global Corruption Index (GCI)	Country scores range from 0 to 100, where 0 corresponds to the lowest level of corruption and 100 to the highest level of corruption.

Control variables. I controlled for GDP and interest rate because both have been found to impact a country's CBDC adoption stage (Maryaningsih et al., 2022; Koparan, 2025).

Variable Type		Variable Name	Measurement	Data Sources
Dependent Variable	Categorical	CBDC adoption stage	Research: 1 Proof of Concept: 2 Pilot: 3 Launched: 4	CBDC Tracker
Control Variable	Continuous	Log GDP	3-year average of log GDP (2022-2024)	World Bank
	Continuous	Interest	Interest rate (2024)	
Independent Variable	Continuous	Institutions	3-year average of Institutions pillar scores (2022-2024)	Global Innovation Index
	Continuous	Human capital and research	3-year average of Human capital and research pillar scores (2022-2024)	
	Continuous	Infrastructure	3-year average of Infrastructure pillar score (2022-2024)	
	Continuous	Market sophistication	3-year average of Market sophistication pillar scores (2022-2024)	
	Continuous	Business sophistication	3-year average of Business sophistication pillar scores (2022-2024)	
	Continuous	Knowledge and technology outputs	3-year average of Knowledge and technology outputs pillar scores (2022-2024)	
	Continuous	Creative outputs	3-year average of Creative pillar scores (2022-2024)	
Moderating Variable	Continuous	Corruption	3-year average of Control of corruption index score (2021-2023)	Worldwide Governance Indicator
	Continuous	Corruption	3-year average of Corruption score (2021-2023)	Corruption Perceptions Index
	Continuous	Corruption	3-year average of Corruption Score (2021-2023)	Global Corruption Index

Data Analysis Procedures

Linear regression is a statistical method used to model the relationship between a dependent (response, outcome) variable and one or more independent (explanatory) variables while controlling for the effects of other variables. The application of the linear regression model (LRM) can only be used in situations where the dependent variable is continuous, not appropriate for categorical outcomes, which are distinct and have no intrinsic order. The CBDC Tracker typically categorizes the current (or historic) status of a CBDC using five types or stages of development. The five common categories are as follows:

- *Cancelled*: The CBDC project has been discontinued due to economic, technical or policy reasons. Note that this study did not include cancelled CBDC initiatives.
- *Research*: Countries that have conducted first explanatory CBDC research, establishing working groups to explore the use cases, impact, and feasibility of a CBDC.
- *Development (Proof of Concept)*: Countries that are in an advanced research stage and have published a CBDC proof of concept, initiating technical build and early testing of a CBDC in controlled environments.
- *Pilot*: Countries that initiated small-scale testing of a CBDC in the real world with a limited number of parties or on a wide scale.
- *Launched*: The CBDC has officially fully launched a CBDC for widespread retail and/or wholesale use.

This study operationalized the dependent variable of a country's CBDC adoption by assigning a value of 1 to *research*, a value of 2 to *development*, a value of 3 to *pilot*, and a value of 4 to *launched* (Auer et al., 2021; Le et al., 2023). I employed ordered logistic regression as a primary statistical method because it is a statistical technique suitable for predicting a categorical variable

(representing a country's CBDC adoption stage) given the multiple independent variables. The ordered logistic regression model can be defined as

$$\text{logit}(P(Y \leq j)) = \beta_{j0} + \beta_{j1}x_1 + \dots + \beta_{jp}x_p$$

for $j = 1, \dots, J-1$ and p predictors. Due to the parallel lines assumption, the intercepts are different for each category but the slopes are constant across categories. The following four assumptions were tested in the sequential order.

Hierarchical Regression

I employed moderated hierarchical regression by adding independent variables in blocks. This helped me to assess the incremental contribution of new variables to explaining the variance in the dependent variable, controlling for the effects of previously entered variables. In the first stage, I included all the control variables (GDP and interest rate) to account for their effects on the dependent variable of CBDC adoption stage before assessing the impact of my independent variables and moderating variables. In the second stage, I added the five national innovation enablers (e.g., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the two national innovation outcomes (e.g., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) separately and then added all the seven variables together. In the third stage, I added the moderator variable of corruption and all the interaction terms.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics for all the variables used in this study. As discussed earlier, I used the CBDC Tracker to operationalize the dependent variable of a country's CBDC adoption stage by assigning a value of 1 to *research*, a value of 2 to *development*, a value of 3 to *pilot*, and a value of 4 to *launched* (Auer et al., 2021; Le et al., 2023). A total of 110 CBDC initiatives were included in the analysis with 81 in the research stage, 23 in the development stage, 19 in the pilot stage, and 4 in the launched stage. As explained earlier, this variable attribute led me to use ordinal logistic regression. I controlled for two variables (i.e., GDP and interest rate). A country's GDP was operationalized as the logarithm value of the 3-year average GDP (2022-2024). A country's interest rate was operationalized using the interest rate for 2024. I employed eight independent variables. Among the seven independent variables related to national innovation capability, institutions had the largest mean of 55.49, while knowledge and technology outputs had the smallest mean of 28.05. The seven independent variables had relatively similar standard deviations, ranging from 13.77 for infrastructure to 18.94 for institutions. The moderating variable of corruption was measured using three corruption indicators—the control of corruption index within the World Governance Indicators (WGI), Corruption Perceptions Index, and Global Corruption Index (GCI). Each of the corruption measures used the 3-year average: 2021-2023 for COCI and GCI and 2022-2024 for CPI.

Table 1 Description Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Dependent Variable</i>					
1. CBDC Adoption Stage	127	1.57	0.86	1.00	4.00
<i>Control Variables</i>					
2. Log GDP	127	11.21	0.97	8.41	13.41
3. Interest Rate	127	8.05	7.44	0.25	50.00
<i>Independent Variables</i>					
4. Institutions	110	55.49	18.94	17.50	97.82
5. Human Capital and Research	110	36.70	16.55	11.30	67.30
6. Infrastructure	110	43.42	13.77	25.30	67.29
7. Market Sophistication	110	38.49	16.84	26.20	81.73
8. Business Sophistication	110	35.35	16.54	15.70	73.23
9. Knowledge and Technology Outputs	110	28.05	16.62	6.20	65.84
10. Creative Outputs	110	28.72	16.51	10.40	63.98
11-1. Corruption (COCI)	127	0.18	1.00	-1.67	2.37
11-2. Corruption (CPI)	122	48.37	18.80	15.00	90.00
11-3. Corruption (GCI)	123	40.01	16.21	7.50	79.56
<i>Moderating Variables</i>					
12-1. Corruption (COCI) x Institutions	110	27.96	67.04	-60.98	204.58
13-1. Corruption (COCI) x Human Capital and Research	110	20.33	47.26	-45.18	139.35
14-1. Corruption (COCI) x Infrastructure	110	19.68	50.96	-44.11	150.60
15-1. Corruption (COCI) x Market Sophistication	110	19.14	48.40	-63.74	139.99
16-1. Corruption (COCI) x Business Sophistication	110	20.17	47.06	-33.36	151.06
17-1. Corruption (COCI) x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	110	17.35	38.97	-30.30	131.46
18-1. Corruption (COCI) x Creative Outputs	110	17.64	39.88	-37.01	127.76
12-2. Corruption (CPI) x Institutions	110	3024.84	2011.17	262.50	8151.33
13-2. Corruption (CPI) x Human Capital and Research	110	2039.04	1538.62	169.50	5290.41
14-2. Corruption (CPI) x Infrastructure	110	2326.48	1475.69	379.50	5717.37
15-2. Corruption (CPI) x Market Sophistication	110	2096.09	1530.18	393.00	5577.90
16-2. Corruption (CPI) x Business Sophistication	110	1974.53	1558.23	235.50	5980.44
17-2. Corruption (CPI) x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	110	1592.24	1396.42	93.00	5376.62
18-2. Corruption (CPI) x Creative Outputs	110	1625.76	1393.51	156.00	5225.33
12-3. Corruption (GCI) x Institutions	110	1906.58	625.64	638.61	3308.94
13-3. Corruption (GCI) x Human Capital and Research	110	1218.18	465.25	394.41	2569.51
14-3. Corruption (GCI) x Infrastructure	110	1512.30	513.50	485.89	2955.02
15-3. Corruption (GCI) x Market Sophistication	110	1315.78	586.20	343.35	3691.33
16-3. Corruption (GCI) x Business Sophistication	110	1161.18	383.92	389.25	2816.59
17-3. Corruption (GCI) x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	110	892.51	412.63	278.71	3017.69
18-3. Corruption (GCI) x Creative Outputs	110	917.59	446.78	306.77	2484.86

Correlations

Table 2 reports correlation coefficients between the dependent variable and the ten independent variables. The dependent variable of CBDC adoption stage is highly correlated with the logarithm value of GDP, human capital and research, business sophistication, knowledge and technology outputs, and creative outputs. There is a moderate to high correlation among the eight independent variables.

Table 2. Correlations

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11-1	11-2	11-3
1. CBDC Adoption Stage	1												
2. Log GDP	.222*	1											
3. Interest Rate	0.142	-0.1	1										
4. Institutions	0.104	.471**	-.521**	1									
5. Human Capital and Research	.227*	.676**	-.332**	.769**	1								
6. Infrastructure	0.17	.673**	-.374**	.830**	.891**	1							
7. Market Sophistication	0.166	.732**	-.324**	.700**	.829**	.807**	1						
8. Business Sophistication	.246**	.676**	-.347**	.777**	.902**	.862**	.839**	1					
9. Knowledge and Technology Outputs	.221*	.736**	-.340**	.662**	.865**	.819**	.841**	.923**	1				
10. Creative Outputs	.310**	.706**	-.237*	.673**	.868**	.831**	.824**	.889**	.904**	1			
11-1. Corruption (COCI)	0.149	.363**	-.463**	.839**	.745**	.747**	.640**	.752**	.674**	.687**	1		
11-2. Corruption (CPI)	0.137	.412**	-.474**	.844**	.764**	.754**	.652**	.768**	.688**	.695**		1	
11-3. Corruption (GCI)	-0.11	-.496**	.433**	-.816**	-.775**	-.786**	-.661**	-.793**	-.733**	-.742**			1

Results of Hypothesis Testing

I tested the four hypotheses using ordinal logistic regression because the dependent variable was an ordinal variable. I employed moderated hierarchical regression analysis. I first entered my control variables in the first step of all analyses (Model 1). Then, I hypothesized my main effects (Hypotheses 1 and 2) in the second step (Models 2, 3, and 4) and interaction effects (Hypotheses 3 and 4) in the third step (Models 5 and 6).

Direct effects. Hypothesis 1 predicted that stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will increase the possibility of advancing to higher stages of CBDC adoption. For any of the five national innovation capability enablers listed above, this hypothesis

was not supported. Hypothesis 2 predicted that stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will increase the possibility of advancing to higher stages of CBDC adoption. This hypothesis was supported for creative outputs ($\beta= 0.067, 0.34$), but not for knowledge and technology outputs.

Table 3. Direct Effects: Hypotheses 1 and 2 with Ordered Logistic Regression

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Log (GDP)	0.587 ** (0.209)	0.482 (0.4)	0.343 (0.346)	0.517 (0.415)
Interest Rate	0.036 (0.023)	0.068 * (0.031)	0.055 * (0.028)	0.049 (0.032)
<i>Direct Effects</i>				
H1 Institutions		-0.002 (0.023)		-0.006 (0.026)
H1 Human Capital and Research		0.01 (0.035)		-0.002 (0.036)
H1 Infrastructure		-0.007 (0.042)		-0.021 (0.042)
H1 Market Sophistication		-0.016 (0.026)		-0.016 (0.027)
H1 Business Sophistication		0.041 (0.032)		0.051 (0.043)
H2 Knowledge and Technology Outputs			-0.027 (0.032)	-0.051 (0.041)
H2 Creative Outputs			0.064 * (0.03)	0.067 * (0.034)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	127	109	109	109
Research	81	68	68	68
Proof of Concept	23	19	19	19
Pilot	19	19	19	19
Launched	4	3	3	3

Interaction effects. Hypothesis 3 predicted that corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. Corruption positively moderated the relationship in the case of institutions and market sophistication, not in the case of human capital and research, infrastructure, and business sophistication.

- Corruption measured using *Control of Corruption*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta= 0.053, 0.05$) and market sophistication ($\beta= -0.061, 0.067$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, and business sophistication.
- Corruption measured using *Corruption Perception Index*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta= 0.003, 0.044$) and market sophistication ($\beta= -0.003, 0.055$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, and business sophistication.
- Corruption measured using *Global Corruption Indicator*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta= -0.003, 0.066$) and market sophistication ($\beta= 0.003, 0.065$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, and business sophistication.

Hypothesis 4 predicted that corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and the adoption of a CBDC. This hypothesis was not supported in the case of either of the two national innovation capability outcomes listed above across the three corruptions measures.

Table 4. Interaction Effects (COCI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 (Ordered Logistic Regression)

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.418 (0.422)	1.15 * (0.532)
Interest Rate	0.053 (0.033)	0.036 (0.037)
Institutions	0.019 (0.035)	0.036 (0.037)
Human Capital and Research	0.003 (0.037)	0.011 (0.038)
Infrastructure	-0.018 (0.043)	-0.068 (0.052)
Market Sophistication	-0.017 (0.027)	-0.037 (0.031)
Business Sophistication	0.055 (0.043)	0.071 (0.053)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	-0.051 (0.041)	-0.05 (0.055)
Creative Outputs	0.071 * (0.034)	0.065 * (0.039)
Corruption [Measurement: Control of Corruption Index]	-0.608 (0.569)	0.269 (1.29)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3 Corruption x Institutions		0.053 * (0.027)
H3 Corruption x Human Capital and Research		-0.033 (0.039)
H3 Corruption x Infrastructure		-0.042 (0.049)
H3 Corruption x Market Sophistication		-0.061 * (0.033)
H3 Corruption x Business Sophistication		0.02 (0.045)
H4 Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs		0.022 (0.043)
H4 Corruption x Creative Outputs		0.009 (0.035)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	109	109
Research	68	68
Proof of Concept	19	19
Pilot	19	19
Launched	3	3

Table 5. Interaction Effects (CPI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 with Ordered Logistic Regression

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.407 (0.422)	1.101 * (0.532)
Interest Rate	0.052 (0.033)	0.037 (0.037)
Institutions	0.023 (0.034)	-0.09 (0.075)
Human Capital and Research	0.007 (0.037)	0.09 (0.105)
Infrastructure	-0.02 (0.043)	0.044 (0.133)
Market Sophistication	-0.018 (0.027)	0.116 (0.087)
Business Sophistication	0.057 (0.044)	0.027 (0.142)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	-0.05 (0.041)	-0.084 (0.147)
Creative Outputs	0.07 * (0.034)	0.025 (0.108)
Corruption [Measurement: Corruption Perceptions Index]	-0.04 (0.031)	0.013 (0.074)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3 Corruption x Institutions		0.003 * (0.001)
H3 Corruption x Human Capital and Research		-0.002 (0.002)
H3 Corruption x Infrastructure		-0.003 (0.003)
H3 Corruption x Market Sophistication		-0.003 * (0.002)
H3 Corruption x Business Sophistication		0.001 (0.003)
H4 Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs		0.001 (0.002)
H4 Corruption x Creative Outputs		0.001 (0.002)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	109	109
Research	68	68
Proof of Concept	19	19
Pilot	19	19
Launched	3	3

Table 6. Interaction Effects (GCI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 with Ordered Logistic Regression

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.481 (0.416)	1.199 * (0.531)
Interest Rate	0.05 (0.033)	0.034 (0.036)
Institutions	0.021 (0.029)	0.173 * (0.079)
Human Capital and Research	0.003 (0.037)	-0.088 (0.105)
Infrastructure	-0.009 (0.043)	-0.209 (0.152)
Market Sophistication	-0.025 (0.027)	-0.196 * (0.086)
Business Sophistication	0.06 (0.044)	0.109 (0.118)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	-0.048 (0.041)	-0.011 (0.1)
Creative Outputs	0.077 * (0.035)	0.161 * (0.091)
Corruption [Measurement: Global Corruption Index]	0.056 * (0.029)	-0.034 (0.079)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3 Corruption x Institutions		-0.003 * (0.002)
H3 Corruption x Human Capital and Research		0.002 (0.002)
H3 Corruption x Infrastructure		0.003 (0.003)
H3 Corruption x Market Sophistication		0.003 * (0.002)
H3 Corruption x Business Sophistication		-0.001 (0.003)
H4 Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs		-0.001 (0.003)
H4 Corruption x Creative Outputs		-0.002 (0.002)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	109	109
Research	68	68
Proof of Concept	19	19
Pilot	19	19
Launched	3	3

Alternative analysis

I transformed the ordered dependent variable into a dichotomous variable by assigning a value of 0 to the CBDC initiatives at the research or proof of concept stage (lower stages) and a value of 1 to the CBDC initiatives at the pilot or launched stage (higher stages). Performing binary logistic regression using the same three-year dataset produced the results as follows.

Direct effects. Hypothesis 1 was not supported in the case of any of the five national innovation capability enablers listed above. Hypothesis 2 was supported in the case of creative outputs ($\beta= 0.094, 0.046$), but in the case of knowledge and technology outputs.

Table 7. Direct Effects: Hypotheses 1 and 2 with Binary Logistic Regression

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Log (GDP)	0.847 *** (0.301)	0.774 (0.58)	0.21 (0.476)	0.804 (0.628)
Interest Rate	0.068 * (0.023)	0.115 * (0.046)	0.107 * (0.043)	0.111 * (0.053)
<i>Direct Effects</i>				
H1 Institutions		0.032 (0.033)		0.05 (0.04)
H1 Human Capital and Research		0.061 (0.049)		0.035 (0.052)
H1 Infrastructure		-0.066 (0.061)		-0.088 (0.063)
H1 Market Sophistication		-0.055 (0.037)		-0.069 (0.04)
H1 Business Sophistication		0.044 (0.044)		-0.009 (0.06)
H2 Knowledge and Technology Outputs			-0.029 (0.042)	0.004 (0.053)
H2 Creative Outputs			0.089 * (0.04)	0.094 * (0.046)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	125	104	104	99
Research or Proof of Concept	103	87	87	84
Pilot or Launched	22	17	17	15

Interaction effects. Hypothesis 3 was supported in the case of institutions, but not in the case of human capital and research, infrastructure, and market sophistication, and business sophistication.

- Corruption measured using *Control of Corruption*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta = 0.101, 0.05$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication.
- Corruption measured using *Corruption Perception Index*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta = 0.006, 0.001$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication.
- Corruption measured using *Global Corruption Indicator*. This hypothesis was supported for institutions ($\beta = -0.008, 0.004$), but not for human capital research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication.

Hypothesis 4 was not supported in the case of either of the two national innovation capability outcomes listed above across the three corruptions measures.

Table 8. Interaction Effects (COCI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 with Binary Logistic Regression

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.674 (0.642)	1.81 * (0.898)
Interest Rate	0.122 * (0.056)	0.085 (0.058)
Institutions	0.082 (0.055)	0.117 (0.066)
Human Capital and Research	0.039 (0.054)	0.072 (0.0071)
Infrastructure	-0.082 (0.064)	-0.213 * (0.091)
Market Sophistication	-0.066 (0.04)	-0.115 * (0.053)
Business Sophistication	-0.011 (0.061)	0.035 (0.088)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	0.004 (0.053)	0 (0.082)
Creative Outputs	0.1 * (0.047)	0.136 * (0.063)
Corruption [Measurement: Control of Corruption Index]	-0.707 (0.824)	0.736 (2.034)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3 Corruption x Institutions		0.101 * (0.05)
H3 Corruption x Human Capital and Research		-0.113 (0.074)
H3 Corruption x Infrastructure		-0.045 (0.079)
H3 Corruption x Market Sophistication		-0.049 (0.051)
H3 Corruption x Business Sophistication		0.008 (0.092)
H4 Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs		-0.01 (0.069)
H4 Corruption x Creative Outputs		0.034 (0.062)
<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	95	95
Research or Proof of Concept	84	84
Pilot or Launched	11	11

Table 9. Interaction Effects (CPI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 with Binary Logistic Regression

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.667 (0.642)	1.892 * (0.937)
Interest Rate	0.122 * (0.056)	0.088 (0.06)
Institutions	0.086 (0.054)	-0.137 (0.128)
Human Capital and Research	0.043 (0.054)	0.396 (0.234)
Infrastructure	-0.083 (0.063)	-0.106 (0.234)
Market Sophistication	-0.067 (0.04)	0.006 (0.137)
Business Sophistication	-0.009 (0.061)	0.027 (0.252)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	0.004 (0.053)	0.07 (0.229)
Creative Outputs	0.102 * (0.047)	0.009 (0.18)
Corruption [Measurement: Corruption Perceptions Index]	-0.046 (0.045)	0.037 (0.119)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3	Corruption x Institutions	0.006 * (0.001)
H3	Corruption x Human Capital and Research	-0.007 (0.002)
H3	Corruption x Infrastructure	-0.003 (0.003)
H3	Corruption x Market Sophistication	-0.003 (0.002)
H3	Corruption x Business Sophistication	0.001 (0.003)
H4	Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	-0.002 (0.002)
H4	Corruption x Creative Outputs	0.003 (0.002)
<hr/>		
	<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	
	98	90
	Research or Proof of Concept	82
	Pilot or Launched	8

Table 10. Interaction Effects (GCI): Hypotheses 3 and 4 with Binary Logistic Regression

	Model 5	Model 6
Log (GDP)	0.7 (0.641)	2.368 * (1.081)
Interest Rate	0.141 * (0.058)	0.082 (0.061)
Institutions	0.106 * (0.05)	0.506 * (0.182)
Human Capital and Research	0.05 (0.057)	-0.253 (0.208)
Infrastructure	-0.066 (0.065)	-0.536 (0.312)
Market Sophistication	-0.081 * (0.039)	-0.355 * (0.163)
Business Sophistication	-0.017 (0.064)	-0.016 (0.28)
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	0.007 (0.055)	-0.002 (0.185)
Creative Outputs	0.125 * (0.051)	0.408 * (0.201)
Corruption [Measurement: Global Corruption Index]	0.098 * (0.043)	-0.112 (0.146)
<i>Interaction Effects</i>		
H3	Corruption x Institutions	-0.008 * (0.004)
H3	Corruption x Human Capital and Research	0.008 (0.005)
H3	Corruption x Infrastructure	0.007 (0.007)
H3	Corruption x Market Sophistication	0.004 (0.003)
H3	Corruption x Business Sophistication	0.002 (0.006)
H4	Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	0 (0.005)
H4	Corruption x Creative Outputs	-0.006 (0.005)
<hr/>		
	<i>Observations (CBDC Adoption Stage)</i>	
	98	97
	Research or Proof of Concept	84
	Pilot or Launched	14
		85
		12

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

General Discussion

Based on the results of hypothesis testing presented in Chapter 4, I provide my interpretation of the results on direct effects and interaction effects, followed by a post hoc analysis.

Direct effects. Analyzing 110 CBDC initiatives by using data gathered from the CBDC Tracker, Global Innovation Index, Global Governance Indicators, Corruption Perceptions Index, and Worldwide Corruption Index. This study found that none of the five national innovation capability enablers—institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication—had statistically significant impact on CBDC adoption. However, creative outputs—one of the two national innovation capability outcomes—were found to increase the possibility of CBDC adoption, although the other national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs) had no statistically significant impact on CBDC adoption. This suggests that countries with high levels of creative outputs including intangible assets (e.g., trademarks, global brands, industrial designs), creative goods and services (e.g., cultural and creative services exports, national feature films, telecom, entertainment and media markets, creative goods exports), and online creativity (e.g, generic and country-code top-level domains (TLDs), Github commits pushes received and sent, and mobile app creation) were more likely to pursue CBDC adoption.

Interaction effects. Corruption was found to play a moderating role in two cases. First, corruption positively moderated the relationship between institutions and CBDC adoption, meaning that the positive relationship between institutions and CBDC adoption was stronger in countries with lower levels of corruption than in those with higher levels of corruption. This suggests that countries with low levels of corruption and strong institutions characterized by

institution environment (e.g., high levels of operational stability and government effectiveness), regulatory environment (high levels of regulatory quality and rule of law), and business environment (high levels of political stability for doing business and entrepreneurship policies and culture) were more likely to adopt CBDC. Second, corruption negatively moderated the relationship between market sophistication and CBDC adoption, meaning that the positive relationship between institutions and CBDC adoption was weaker in countries with higher levels of corruption than in those with lower levels of corruption. This suggests that countries with high levels of corruption and market sophistication characterized by credit (e.g., high levels of finance for startups and scaleups, domestic credit to private sector, and loans from all microfinance institutions), investment (high levels of market capitalization, venture capital investors, venture capital recipients, venture capital received), and trade, diversification and market scale (e.g., high levels of tariff rate applied, domestic industry diversification, and domestic market scale measured by GDP).

Post hoc analysis. The study performed three robust tests. First, I created a five-year average dataset separately from the three-year average dataset used for this study. Testing the four hypotheses using the five-year average dataset produced similar results. Second, I transformed the dependent variable used for this study into a dichotomous variable by assigning “0” to the CBDC initiatives at the research or proof of concept stage and “1” to the CBDC initiatives at the pilot or launched stage. Performing binary logistic regression using the three-year or five-year average dataset produced similar results as well. Third, I tested Hypotheses 3 and 4 using three different corruption measures based on the data from the GCI, CPI, and WGI, respectively. This triangulation helped to verify consistent patterns of how corruption positively moderated the relationship between institutions and CBDC adoption and negatively moderated

the relationship between market sophistication and CBDC adoption pbetween oderating role of corruption across the three measures.

Implications for Practitioners

I expect that three groups of companies may benefit the most from the study findings. Financial institutions can determine investment strategies regarding countries and companies operating in the CBDC industry. Multinational corporations can refine their digital payment and risk management strategies. For example, they can offer cross-border payments compatible with CBDCs. Third, tech companies competing in the digital infrastructure industry can acquire insights regarding the likelihood of CBDC adoptions in various nations to determine when to enter new markets.

As for senior executives in economics and finance, they can benefit from the study findings as followa. First, they can better analyze the pros and cons of participating in various CBDC ecosystems worldwide. Second, they can better develop a practical framework for assessing the likelihood of CBDC adoption in specific markets and integrate it into long-term strategic planning for their current and potential markets. Third, they can provide better guidelines for asset valuations and investment portfolios associated with CBDCs when they enter a CBDC market as a consumer or intermediary. Fourth, they can better manage financial risks in various countries and optimize portfolio strategies in response to emerging digital currency trends around the globe.

Limitations of the Study

The study has a few limitations. First, combining the five archival data sources resulted in incomplete data for certain countries. While I was able to gather complete data for 127 initiative's CBDC adoption stage and their corresponding countries' GDP and interest rate, the

following countries did not have available data for operationalizing national innovation capability enablers/outcomes and/or corruption.

Country	CBDC Adoption Stage	CBDC Type
Bhutan	Research	Retail, Wholesale
Malawi	Research	Retail
Sudan	Research	Retail
Aruba	Research	Retail
Bahamas	Launched	Retail
Eswatini	Research	Retail
Haiti	Research	Retail
Macau	Proof of concept	Retail
Maldives	Research	Retail
Palau	Proof of concept	Others
Palestine	Research	Retail
Qatar	Proof of concept	Wholesale
Solomon Islands	Research	Retail
Solomon Islands	Proof of concept	Retail
Taiwan	Research	Retail, Wholesale
Tanzania	Research	Retail, Wholesale
Tonga	Research	Retail
Vanuatu	Research	Retail

A careful treatment of missing data is a crucial step in data analysis because missing values can lead to biased results and inaccurate conclusions if not handled properly. Common approaches to treat missing data include deletion, imputation, and model-based techniques. Listwise deletion involves removing entire rows (cases) containing any missing values. This is simple but can lead to significant data loss, especially if many values are missing. Pairwise

deletion uses all available data for each analysis, potentially leading to different sample sizes for different analyses. Given that the sample size of the study was relatively small, I applied pairwise deletion in performing moderated hierarchical regression.

Second, a common statistical problem that arises in a multiple regression model is multicollinearity (Belsley et al., 1980). Multicollinearity occurs when two or more independent variables in a multiple regression model are highly intercorrelated. This means that one independent variable can be linearly predicted from the others with a non-trivial degree of accuracy. Multicollinearity invalidates some of the basic assumptions underlying the model's mathematical estimation. The presence of multicollinearity can produce large variances for parameter estimates and high standard errors. If extreme correlation occurs among independent variables, parameter estimates become unreliable (Lewis-Beck, 1980). In addition, if severe multicollinearity exists, regression coefficients obtained in one sample are unreliable if applied to the overall population. Thus, when multicollinearity is present, the confounded effects of independent variables make the importance of independent variables more difficult to determine (Stevens, 1992). Hence, I examined variance inflation factor (VIF) scores for all the independent variables to determine if multicollinearity was an issue in my multiple regression models. In the majority of the variables, the VIF exceeded 6.5, suggesting that multicollinearity was an issue (Hair et al., 1995; Ryan, 1997). To mitigate multicollinearity, I employed mean centering, which yielded stronger coefficients.

Recommendations for Future Research

The study has a few implications for future research. As discussed earlier, money can be classified into 11 categories (Bech & Garratt, 2017), two of which are retail CBDCs accessible to the general public and wholesale CBDCs available only to financial institutions. This study

examined a total of 127 CBDC initiatives: 90 (retail), 24 (wholesale), 10 (retail/wholesale), and 3 (others) without distinguishing retail CBDCs from whole CBDCs. Future studies could examine the impact of national innovation capability enablers or outcomes using a more refined sample (e.g., retail CBDCs) or controlling for potential effects due to the differences between retail and whole CBDCS by creating a dichotomous dummy variable by assigning 0 to retail CBDCs and 1 to non-retail CBDCs.

In creating my dataset, I included the CBDC initiatives that were pursued at the country level because the unit of analysis for my study was a national economy. This led to excluding CBDC initiatives pursued by groups of countries and/or region. For example, Stella is a CBDC initiative—at the research stage—which is jointly pursued by the European Central Bank and Bank of Japan to explore the opportunity for using DLT to improve financial market infrastructure to support payment and securities settlement. This joint project consists of four phases. In phase 1 distributed ledger technology (DLT) was used to process large-scale payments. In phase 2 securities settlement in a DLT environment were tested. In phase 3, DLT-related technologies were applied to increase the efficiency of cross-border payments. In phase 4 concentrated on the auditability and confidentiality of settlement assets, like CBDC, in a DLT environment. Another example is mBridge, a joint CBDC initiative at the pilot stage that involves the Central Banks of China, Thailand, the United Arab Emirates, and Hong Kong. mBridge is a multiple central bank platform developed to support real-time, peer-to-peer, cross border payments and foreign exchange transactions using CBDCs based on a blockchain called the mBridge Ledger. During the six-week pilot period, sample trade settlement transactions were conducted on the trial platform among the four participating central banks, selected commercial banks, and their customers across 11 industries.

Future studies could conduct research on the potential of CBDCs to improve cross-border payments. Cross-border CBDC initiatives are believed to reduce transaction costs, improve efficiency, enhance financial inclusion, and promote innovation in payment systems (Themistocleous et al., 2023). However, there are still issues with establishing robust regulatory frameworks, addressing privacy and security concerns, ensuring interoperability between different systems, and navigating potential impacts on the existing financial infrastructure.

Conclusion

Economists argue that the basic concept of money is being challenged by the introduction of digital currency (Aysan & Kayani, 2021). The Chinese Central Bank has decided to move forward with the issuance of a completely digital currency. The effort of introducing a digital renminbi (digital yuan) is to reduce the dependence on the U.S. dollar. The strategy of being the first mover or pioneer of implementing a digital currency is to leverage their position in the world and take advantage of invoicing trade through a digital yuan rather than the United States dollar which is the current reserve currency. Another goal of the Chinese government issuing their own central bank digital currency is to reduce the power of private entities in their own country. WeChat Pay and Alipay are the largest private entities in China that are used for digital transactions and widely adopted across their country. The issuance of the digital yuan and the implementation of this technology by the central bank is to have complete control over the money supply by diminishing private entity's ability to transact.

The ramification of this for the entire world is concerning. In China's case, this technology allows for the complete surveillance of transaction and creates a large database for this transaction to be tracked. The database of all transactions will give China the ability to better track global markets, and the value produced with each good. The threat of China being the

pioneer of this technology is primarily concerning to liberal democracies around the world who have been late to act in the development of digital currencies (CBDCs). If there were to be wider spread adoption of the digital yuan, it would position China to dominate the world economy and reap massive financial gains (Aysan & Kayani, 2021).

To combat the Chinese development of the digital yuan, there is a case being made for a digital dollar (CBDC) at home in the United States (Ney, 2020). The two largest values a digital dollar provides are financial security and the geopolitical reality that China has moved forward with their own digital currency. One of the most notable impacts for domestic financial stability to improve safety of the U.S. economy. If American citizens were to shift their deposits from commercial banks to holding these funds with the central bank this would decrease the risk allocation of funds. For example, when consumers hold their deposits at banks the money is insured by the FDIC (Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation). The insurance is supposed to protect the consumer from risks of the bank potentially defaulting. The problem with the current structure is that the insurance fund only currently totals 41 billion dollars, the fund is supposed to cover 6 trillion in deposits. The current \$250,000 deposit cap could only cover a mere 0.006 percent of all the deposits that are kept in banks. Therefore, we saw the federal government rush to bail out the banks in 2008. Without the bailout banks would have gone under and the FDIC insurance that existed would not be able to reimburse consumer losses.

The most important argument for a digital dollar is the international interests of America. The influence of the American is broken up into two pieces (Ney, 2022). The first is the overall strength of the US economy, its ability to withstand financial shock like the 2008 financial crisis and most importantly, its ability to maintain the world's global reserve currency. The second is

the financial infrastructure of our payment processing capabilities. The singlehanded largest threat to our dominance over the financial infrastructure is China launching their own.

The development of Bitcoin prompted central banks to act and develop Central Bank Digital Currencies. The technology isn't yet widely implemented and there are questions about if the public will buy into a digital currency issued by the central banks. In the research article, *Conventionalists, Pioneers and Criminals Choosing Between a National Currency and a Global Currency* the authors look to analyze this using game theory (Wang et al., 2021). Participants in this study were broken up into three categories based on key criteria: conventionalists, pioneers, and criminals. The study, specifically, analyzed if the players would choose between a national currency (CBDC) or a global currency (Bitcoin, decentralization of currency not controlled by governments). The study found that only one of the groups, conventionalists, would adapt and use a national currency (CBDC) as opposed to the other two groups opting to use a decentralized currency. Conclusions from the study were that even if central banks were to widespread adopt this technology, a large portion of society may not "buy in" which creates a much larger conversation.

One of the largest arguments against CBDCs is our individual privates' rights (Bindseil, 2019). Should countries move forward with a digital currency or are there huge implications for control that governments will have over the financial system and individuals? "Considerations of 'privacy' in the context of CBDCs extend beyond a traditional notion of freedom from intrusion into private lives seen as 'fundamental to human dignity and flourishing,' and encompass concerns traditionally embodied in the concept of 'data protection,' such as control over personal information and resisting surveillance (Rennie & Steele, 2021)." There are four fundamental privacy risks/losses (Rennie & Steele, 2021). The first is loss of anonymity which is the

reduction in freedoms that are associated with physical cash. Physical cash offers anonymity because once it's in circulation there isn't an easy way for governments to track how and where this money is being used. CBDCs will eliminate the anonymity of transactions, and this currency has the potential for governments to be able to track everything. The second is loss of liberty because of the exposure to surveillance and monitoring by governments. Governments issuing a completely digital currency will give them data about how this money is being used, which would allow them to track and store the information. The third is loss of individual control, our ability to control our personal information and transactions. The fourth is the potential loss of regulatory control. This becomes problematic when digital currencies are the only option to transact. Specifically, internationally when foreign governments or different jurisdictions have rules and regulations for control.

This study highlights the three national innovation characteristics (i.e., institutions, market sophistication, and creative outputs) and corruption as important factors affecting a country's advancement to higher stages of CBDC adoption. The largest argument against the current system is that cash is incredibly costly as well as very prone to theft, counterfeiting and the main vehicle for money laundering across and tax evasion across the globe (Alonso et al., 2021). Central bank digital currencies are thought to combat these problems and are the largest arguments for adopting a digital currency. The goal of broader implementation of a CBDC is that households and business will adopt and make payments with a completely electronic form of currency payments. It is likely that CBDCs will eventually compete with crypto currencies and stablecoins. Yet, whether households (citizens) will choose to consume a CBDC as opposed to the traditional currency if all three of them become viable options (Wang & Hausken, 2022) remains to be seen. Right now, households typically hold their funds with banks that offer the

highest interest rate (rate of return) on their money. With CBDCs households will essentially have the option to hold their money with the central bank resulting in competition between traditional banks and the central bank. This will result in the central bank competing with banks for their interest rate.

REFERENCES

- Adrian, T., & Mancini-Griffoli, T. (2021). The rise of digital money. *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, 13(1), 57-77.
- Agresti, A. (2013). *Categorical data analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Ahiabenu, K., & Olaleye, S. A. (2024). The views of regulators around the world: A systematic review of central bank's official publications on CBDC. *Global Developments in Central Bank Digital Currency*, 32-53.
- Alfar, A. J. K., Kumpamool, C., Nguyen, D. T. K., & Ahmed, R. (2023). The determinants of issuing central bank digital currencies. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2023.101884>
- Alonso, N., S. L., Jorge-Vazquez, J., & Reier Forradellas, R. F. (2021). Central Banks Digital Currency: Detection of Optimal Countries for the Implementation of a CBDC and the Implication for Payment Industry Open Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market and Complexity*, 7(72), 72.

- Aysan, A., & Kayani, F. (2022). China's transition to a digital currency does it threaten dollarization? *Asia and the Global Economy*, 2(1).
- Banerjee, S., & Sinha, M. (2025). The policy endorsement of central bank digital currency-trend analysis and research scope using bibliometric review. *International Journal of Management Practice*, 18(1), 64-91.
- Barker, James, Clayton, Emily, Dyson, Ben, & Meaning, Jack. 2021. Broadening Narrow Money: Monetary Policy with a Central Bank Digital Currency. *International Journal of Central Banking*.
- Bech, M. L., & Garratt, R. (2017). Central bank cryptocurrencies. *BIS Quarterly Review* September.
- Bhutta, Muhammad Nasir, et al. "Towards Secure IoT-Based Payments by Extension of Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard (PCI DSS)." *Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing*, 24 Jan. 2022, pp. 1–10.
- Bindseil, U. (2019). Central Bank Digital Currency: Financial System Implications and Control. *International Journal of Political Economy*, 48(4), 303–335.
- Bjerg, O. (2017). Designing new money-the policy trilemma of central bank digital currency.
- Bjorvatn, K., & Søreide, T. (2005). Corruption and privatization. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 21(4), 903-914.
- Bindseil, U., & Senner, R. (2024). Macroeconomic modelling of CBDC: A critical review. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4782993>.
- Bliss, C., & Tella, R. D. (1997). Does competition kill corruption? *Journal of Political Economy*, 105(5), 1001-1023.

- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. 2015. *Business research methods*. Oxford, UK: Oxford university press.
- Carapella, F., & Flemming, J. (2020). Central bank digital currency: A literature review.
- Ceylan, F. A. (2024). A review of Central Bank Digital Currency: Current status and changing trends. *İzmir İktisat Dergisi*, 39(2), 568-589.
- Cieślak, A., & Goczek, Ł. (2018). Control of corruption, international investment, and economic growth—Evidence from panel data. *World development*, 103, 323-335.
- CPMI. (2015). Digital currencies. Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures, Bank for International Settlements, Basel, Switzerland.
- Dionysopoulos, L., Marra, M., & Urquhart, A. (2024). Central bank digital currencies: A critical review. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 91.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.103031>
- Dong, Z., Umar, M., Yousaf, U. B., & Muhammad, S. (2024). Determinants of central bank digital currency adoption—a study of 85 countries. *Journal of Economic Policy Reform*, 27(3), 316-330.
- Edquist, C. (2005). Systems of innovation: perspectives and challenges. In Fagerberg, J., Mowery, D. C., & Nelson, R. R. (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of innovation*. Oxford University Press.
- Fahad, S., & Bulut, M. (2024). Central bank digital currencies: A comprehensive systematic literature review on worldwide research emergence and methods used. *American Journal of Business*, 39(3), 137-157. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJB-12-2023-0210>
- Freeman, C. (1987). *Technology policy and economic performance: Lessons from Japan*. Science Policy Research Unit University of Sussex and Pinter Publishers.

Freeman, C. (1995). "The 'National System of Innovation' in historical perspective". *Cambridge Journal of Economics*: 5–24.

Gene, H. O., & Takagi, S. (2024). A literature review on the design and implementation of central bank digital currencies. *International Journal of Economic Policy Studies*, 18(1), 197-225.

Ghosh, K., & Das, P. K. (2024). Central bank digital currencies: A bibliometric analysis on research themes in pursuit of research trends. *International Journal of Law and Management*.

Griffoli, T., Peria, M. S. M., Agur, I., Ari, A., Kiff, J., Popescu, A., & Rochon, C. (2018). Casting light on central bank digital currency. *IMF Staff Discussion Notes*, 18(08), 1.

Group of Central Banks. (2020). Central bank digital currencies: foundational principles and core features. <https://www.bis.org/publ/othp33.pdf>.

Hsu, Y., Hartauer, C., & Nugroho, D. P. (2023). Adoption of Retail Central Bank Digital Currencies with a Focus on User-Centricity. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 14(6).

Hsu, Y., Hartauer, C., & Nugroho, D. P. (2023). Adoption of retail central bank digital currencies with a focus on user-centricity. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 14(6).

Jun, J., & Yeo, E. (2021). Central bank digital currency, loan supply, and bank failure risk: a microeconomic approach. *Financial Innovation*, 7(1), 1–22.

Kacker, M., & Sinha, M. (2024). Institutional quality and CBDC development: A cross-country analysis. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4909888>.

- Kahn, C. M., & Roberds, W. (2009). Why pay? An introduction to payments economics. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 18(1), 1-23.
- Kaufmann, Daniel and Kraay, Aart, The Worldwide Governance Indicators: Methodology and 2024 Update (November 05, 2024).
<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099005210162424110>, Available at SSRN:
<https://ssrn.com/abstract=5154675> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5154675>
- Kiff, M. J., Alwazir, J., Davidovic, S., Farias, A., Khan, M. A., Khiaonarong, M. T., ... & Zhou, P. (2020). A survey of research on retail central bank digital currency. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3639760> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3639760>
- Koonprasert, T. T., Kanada, S., Tsuda, N., Reshidi, E. (2024). Central bank digital currency adoption: Inclusive strategies for intermediaries and users.” IMF Fintech Note 2024/005, International Monetary Fund, Washington, DC.
- Koparan, A. (2025). Central Bank Digital Currencies: A review of global trends in adoption, financial inclusion, and the role of country characteristics. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 22(1), 107-121.
- Kumhof, M., & Noone, C. (2021). Central bank digital currencies—Design principles for financial stability. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 71, 553-572.
- Kvedaravičiūtė, E., & Šapkauskienė, A. (2024). Development of central bank digital currencies: A bibliometric analysis. *EuroMed Journal of Business*.
- Le, T., Tran, S. H., Nguyen, D. T., & Ngo, T. (2023). The degrees of central bank digital currency adoption across countries: A preliminary analysis. *Economics and Business Letters*, 12(2).

- Long, J. S., & Freese, J. (2006). *Regression models for categorical dependent variables using Stata* (Vol. 7). Stata press.
- Lundvall, B. A. (1985). Product innovation and user-producer interaction. *The Learning Economy and the Economics of Hope*, 19(2), 19-60.
- Lundvall, B. A. (1988). From user-producer interaction to the national system of innovation. In Dosi, G., Freeman, C., Nelson, R., Silverberg, G., & Soete, L. (Eds.), *Technical change and economic theory*. Pinter.
- Lundvall, B. A. (1992). *National systems of innovation: Towards a theory of innovation and interactive learning*. Francis Printer.
- Lundvall, B. Å. (2010). Scope, style, and theme of research on knowledge and learning societies. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1, 18-23.
- Luu, H. N., Do, D. D., Pham, T., Ho, V. X., & Dinh, Q. A. (2023). Cultural values and the adoption of central bank digital currency. *Applied Economics Letters*, 30(15), 2024-2029.
- Mahroum, S., & Al-Saleh, Y. (2013). Towards a functional framework for measuring national innovation efficacy. *Technovation*, 33(10-11), 320-332.
- Mahroum, S., Huggins, R., Clayton, N., Pain, K., & Taylor, P. (2008). Innovation by adoption: Measuring and mapping absorptive capacity in UK nations and regions. *National Endowment for Science, Technology and the Arts*.
- Makridis, C. (2024). The rise of central bank digital currencies: Exploring adoption determinants and early macroeconomic and well-being impacts. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4932810>

- Mani Yekta, M. R., Rabiei, M., & Derakhshan, S. A. (2024). Factors affecting the Issuance of Central Bank Cryptocurrency (Token-based CBDC). *Journal of Industrial and Systems Engineering*, 16(4), 103-120.
- Maryaningsih, N., Nazara, S., Kacaribu, F. N., & Juhro, S. M. (2022). Central bank digital currency: what factors determine its adoption? *Bulletin of Monetary Economics and Banking*, 25(1), 1-24.
- McCullagh, P. (1980). Regression models for ordinal data. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 42(2), 109-127.
- McLeod, S. A. 2007. *Experimental design*. (www.simplypsychology.org/experimental-designs.html). Accessed March 13, 2025.
- Meaning, J., Dyson, B., Barker, J., & Clayton, E. (2018). Broadening narrow money: monetary policy with a central bank digital currency.
- Metcalfe, S. (1995). "The Economic Foundations of Technology Policy: Equilibrium and Evolutionary Perspectives". *Handbook of the economics of innovations and technological change*. Stoneman, Paul. Oxford, UK: Blackwell.
- Mikhalev, I., Burchardi, K., Struchkov, I., Song, B., & Gross, J. 2021. CBDC Tracker. <https://cbdctracker.org/cbdc-tracker-whitepaper.pdf>
- Mohammed, M. A., De-Pablos-Heredero, C., & Montes Botella, J. L. (2023). Exploring the factors affecting countries' adoption of blockchain-enabled central bank digital currencies. *Future Internet*, 15(10), 321. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi15100321>
- Mohammed, M. A., De-Pablos-Heredero, C., & Montes Botella, J. L. (2024). The role of financial sanctions and financial development factors on central bank digital currency implementation. *FinTech*, 3(1), 135-150.

- Nelson, R. R. (1993). *National innovation systems: A comparative analysis*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nelson, R. R., & Winter, S. G. (1982). The Schumpeterian tradeoff revisited. *The American economic review*, 72(1), 114-132.
- Ney, J. (2020). The Case for a Digital Dollar: Security at Home and Abroad. *Harvard Kennedy School Review*, 20, 74–78.
- Ngo, V. M., Van Nguyen, P., Nguyen, H. H., Tram, H. X. T., & Hoang, L. C. (2023). Governance and monetary policy impacts on public acceptance of CBDC adoption. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 64.
- Nasir, M. H., & Zhang, S. (2024). Evaluating innovative factors of the global innovation index: A panel data approach. *Innovation and Green Development*, 3(1), 100096.
- Ogachi, D., Mugambi, P., Bares, L., & Zeman, Z. (2021). Idiosyncrasies of Money: 21st Century Evolution of Money. *Economies*, 9(40), 40.
- Ozili, P. K. (2023). Central bank digital currency research around the world: A review of literature. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 26(2), 215-226.
- Patel, Parimal (1994). "The nature and economic importance of national innovations systems". *STI Review*. STI review. - Paris : OECD, ISSN 1010-5247, ZDB-ID 284967-7. - 1994, p. 9-32. Paris: 9–32.
- Petare, P. A., Josyula, H. P., Landge, S. R., Gatala, S. K. K., & Gunturu, S. R. (2024). Central bank digital currencies: Exploring the future of money and banking. *Migration Letters*, 21(S7), 640-651.
- Prodan, S., Konhäusner, P., Dabija, D. C., Lazaroiu, G., & Marincean, L. (2024). The rise in popularity of central bank digital currencies: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 10(9).

- Ragin, C. C. (2008). What is qualitative comparative analysis?.
- Rennie, E., & Steele, S. (2021). Privacy and Emergency Payments in a Pandemic: How to Think about Privacy and a Central Bank Digital Currency. *Law, Technology and Humans*, 3(1), 6–17.
- Shen, W., & Hou, L. (2021). China’s central bank digital currency and its impacts on monetary policy and payment competition: Game changer or regulatory toolkit? *Computer Law & Security Review*, 41,
- Son, J., Bilgin, M. H., & Ryu, D. (2022). Consumer choices under new payment methods. *Financial Innovation*, 8(1), 1–22.
- Themistocleous, M., da Cunha, P. R., Tabakis, E., & Papadaki, M. (2023). Towards cross-border CBDC interoperability: insights from a multivocal literature review. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 36(5), 1296-1318.
- Umar, M., Shahzad, F., Iqbal, A., & Tong, F. (2024). Does institutional quality matter for central bank digital currency adoption? *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 83, 378-389.
- Venturi, G. C. (2024). Central bank digital currency: Motivations, design, and policy debate. A literature review. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4931365>.
- Wang, H., & Buckley, R. (2023). The Coming Central Bank Digital Currency Revolution and the E-CNY. *Singapore Journal of Legal Studies*, pp. 145–172.
- Wang, G., & Hausken, K. (2021). Conventionalists, Pioneers and Criminals Choosing Between a National Currency and a Global Currency. *Journal of Banking & Financial Economics*, 2(16), 104–133.
- World Intellectual Property Organization. (2024). *Global Innovation Index 2024: Unlocking the promise of social g entrepreneurship*. Geneva, Switzerland. .

Yekta, M. R., Rabiei, M., & Derakhshan, S. A. (2024). Factors affecting the Issuance of Central Bank Cryptocurrency (Token-based CBDC). *Journal of Industrial and Systems Engineering*, 16(4), 103-120.

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11-1	11-2	11-3
1. CBDC Adoption Stage	1												
2. Log GDP	.222*	1											
3. Interest Rate	0.142	-0.097	1										
4. Institutions	0.104	.471**	-.521**	1									
5. Human Capital and Research	.227*	.676**	-.332**	.769**	1								
6. Infrastructure	0.17	.673**	-.374**	.830**	.891**	1							
7. Market Sophistication	0.166	.732**	-.324**	.700**	.829**	.807**	1						
8. Business sophistication	.246**	.676**	-.347**	.777**	.902**	.862**	.839**	1					
9. Knowledge and Technology Outputs	.221*	.736**	-.340**	.662**	.865**	.819**	.841**	.923**	1				
10. Creative outputs	.310**	.706**	-.237*	.673**	.868**	.831**	.824**	.889**	.904**	1			
11-1. Corruption (COC)	0.149	.363**	-.463**	.839**	.745**	.747**	.640**	.752**	.674**	.687**	1		
11-2. Corruption (CPI)	0.137	.412**	-.474**	.844**	.764**	.754**	.652**	.768**	.688**	.695**		1	
11-3. Corruption (CPI)	-0.108	-.496**	.433**	-.816**	-.775**	-.786**	-.661**	-.793**	-.733**	-.742**			1

Hypothesis 1. Stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC.

Institutions	Not supported
Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Infrastructure	Not supported
Market Sophistication	Not supported
Business Sophistication	Not supported

Hypothesis 2. Stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC.

Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Creative Outputs	Supported ($\beta = 0.067, 0.05$)

Hypothesis 3. Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the adoption of a CBDC.

Corruption measured using <i>Control of Corruption</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta = 0.053, 0.05$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Supported ($\beta = -0.061, 0.067$)
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Corruption Perception Index</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta = 0.003, 0.044$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Supported ($\beta = -0.003, 0.055$)
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Global Corruption Indicator</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta = -0.003, 0.066$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Supported ($\beta = 0.003, 0.065$)
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported

Hypothesis 4. Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and the adoption of a CBDC.	
Corruption measured using <i>Control of Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Corruption Perception Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Global Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported

Bi Logistic

Hypothesis 1. Stronger national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC.	
Institutions	Not supported
Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Infrastructure	Not supported
Market Sophistication	Not supported
Business Sophistication	Not supported

Hypothesis 2. Stronger national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) will increase the possibility of adopting a CBDC.	
Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Creative Outputs	Supported ($\beta= 0.089, 0.04$)

Hypothesis 3. Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability enablers (i.e., institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication) and the adoption of a CBDC.	
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Corruption measured using <i>Control of Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta= 0.101, 0.05$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Corruption Perception Index</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta= 0.006, 0.001$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Global Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Institutions	Supported ($\beta= -0.008, 0.004$)
Corruption x Human Capital and Research	Not supported
Corruption x Infrastructure	Not supported
Corruption x Market Sophistication	Not supported
Corruption x Business Sophistication	Not supported

Hypothesis 4. Corruption moderates the relationship between the national innovation capability outcomes (i.e., knowledge and technology outputs and creative outputs) and the adoption of a CBDC.	
Corruption measured using <i>Control of Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Corruption Perception Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported
Corruption measured using <i>Global Corruption Index</i>	
Corruption x Knowledge and Technology Outputs	Not supported
Corruption x Creative Outputs	Not supported

